

Deliverable D7.2 – Completed Policy review and mapping and field research activities

OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results

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Abbreviations

ACP – Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics

ACPD – Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions

ACUMEN – Academic Careers Understood through Measurement and Norms

AEF – Anderson Elffers Felix

AgID – Agency for Digital Italy

AISA – Association for the Promotion of Open Science (Associazione Italiana per la promozione della Scienza Aperta)

ANVUR – Italian Agency for Research Assessment

APCs – Article Processing Charges

AT2OA – Austrian Transition to Open Access

ATT – Open Science and Research Initiative

AWTI – Advisory Council for Science, Technology and Innovation

BEIS – Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy

BMBF – Federal Ministry of Education and Research

BMC – Biomed Central

BMJ – British Medical Journal

CALC – Cyprus Academic Library Consortium

CNR – National Research Council

CRUI – Conference of Italian Universities Rectors

DANS – Data Archiving and Networked Services

DFG – German Research Foundation

DG – Director-General

DH – Digital Humanities

DHA – Digital Humanities Austria

DINI – German Initiative for Network Information

DORA – San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment

EASE – European Association of Science Editors

EC – European Commission

EKT – National Documentation Centre

eLABa – Lithuanian Academic e-Library

EOSC – European Open Science Cloud

ERAC – European Research Area Committee

ERC – European Research Council

ETD – Electronic Theses and Dissertations

ETIS – Estonian Research Information System

EU – European Union

EUDAT – European Data Infrastructure
F1000 – Faculty of 1000
FESTA – Female Empowerment in Science and Technology Academia
FWF – Austrian Research Fund
GEPs – Gender Equality Plans
GS1EU – Gender Summit 1 EU
GYA – Global Young Academy
HEAL-Link – Hellenic Academic Libraries Link
HEFCE – Higher Education Funding Council for England
HEIs – Higher Education Institutions
HEP – High Energy Physics
HLEG – High-Level Expert Group
HRS4R – Human Resources Strategy for Researchers
HUNRO – HUNGarian Open Repositories Consortium
ID – Innovative Dissemination
INFN – National Institute of Nuclear Physics
ISS – National Institute of Health in Italy
JIF – Journal Impact Factor
KEMÖ – Austrian Library Consortium Cooperation E-Media Austria
KNAW – Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
LAS – Lithuanian Academy of Sciences
MES – Ministry for Education and Science
MIDAS – National Open Access Research Data Archive
MS – Member State
NDLR – National Digital Learning Repository
NHS – National Health Service
NOAD – National Open Access Desk
NORA – Norwegian Open Research Archives
NWO – Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research
OA – Open Access
OANA – Open Access Network Austria
OAW – Austrian Academy of Sciences
OBVSG – Austrian Library Network Ltd
OK-AT – Austrian Chapter of Open Knowledge
OPR – Open Peer Review
ORD – Open Research Data
ORD@CH – Open Research Data Platform Switzerland
OS – Open Science

OS-CAM – Open Science Career Assessment Matrix
OSJ – Open Science Journal
OSPP – Open Science Policy Platform
PCOD – Predicted Crystallography Open Database
PIs – Principal Investigators
PLEIADI – Portal for Italian Electronic Scholarly Literature in Institutional Archives
RCAAP – Portugal Open Access Science Repository (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal)
RCL – Research Council of Lithuania
RCUK – Research Councils UK
RDM – Research Data Management
re3data.org –Registry of Research Data Repositories
REF – Research Excellence Framework
RFO – Research Funding Organisations
RISE – Research Information Systems Exchange group
ROARMAP – Registry of Open Access Repository Mandates and Policies
RPOs – Research Performing Organisations
RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation
SAGER – Sex and Gender Equity in Research
SAGW – Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences
SEP – Standard Evaluation Protocol
SERI – State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation
SERSCIDA – Support for Establishment of National/Regional Social Sciences Data
SHERPA – Securing a Hybrid Environment for Research Preservation and Access
SIR – Scientific Independence of Young Researchers
SMEs – Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises
SNF – Swiss National Science Foundation
STEM – Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
swissuniversities – Rectors' Conference of Swiss Higher Education Institutions
SWOT – Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
TU Delft – Delft University of Technology
UCL – University College London
UKCORR – UK Council of Research Repositories
UNIKO – Universities Austria
UvA-DARE – University of Amsterdam Digital Academic Repository
VSNU – Association of Universities in the Netherlands
WP – Work Package
WPL – Work Package Leader

Summary

This report reviews and maps European policies relating to Open Science in order to identify areas where OpenUP's findings and recommendations could support policy-makers and other stakeholders promoting Open Science uptake. The review particularly focuses on policies and initiatives in areas of open peer review, innovative dissemination, altmetrics as well as issues related to gender equality in research and academia.

It is structured into eight sections. Section 1 provides a general introduction to the deliverable. Sections 2 and 3 present the findings of desk research and analysis of available literature on European Commission's priorities for Open Science and national policies and initiatives in this area. Current initiatives related to the key topics of the OpenUP project (open peer review, innovative dissemination, altmetrics and gender in research) are presented and analysed in more detail in Section 4. This section also incorporates the results of the semi-structured interviews conducted with national stakeholders and other experts as well as the results of the OpenUP survey. Section 5 maps national policies and initiatives across eight selected European countries. The overviews focus on Open Access (OA), research data management (RDM) as well as policies and initiatives in the key areas of OpenUP project, including Open Peer Review (OPR), innovative dissemination, altmetrics and gender. The final section 6 outlines conclusions and next steps in WP7, Section 7 contains the bibliography and Section 8 contains annexes.

Desk research and interview material point to an RRI landscape that is still developing across European countries. The European Commission is actively investigating and monitoring various aspects of Open Science through such initiatives as European Open Science Cloud and the Open Science Policy Platform. Several expert groups and working groups have been established by the EC to produce recommendations for several areas of Open Science that are still at nascent stages but already taken up by some researchers and other actors in the academic world.

This deliverable provides an overall synthesis of the results of the research activities conducted under WP7 and has laid the foundation for further work that will be conducted in OpenUP to produce the final policy recommendations. In the next months, the results from all the work packages of OpenUP will be coordinated and assembled into first drafts of policy reports (D7.3 and D7.4). These reports will provide brief overviews of key areas studies by OpenUP and present draft conclusions and recommendations for advancing OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics as well as advancing more gender balanced research ecosystem. They will then be assessed by Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats analysis to identify the key recommendations that could be implemented in different European countries and research systems. The final set of recommendations will be presented and validated in the final OpenUP workshop that will involve participants from national and EU level policy makers, funders, librarians, infrastructure providers, research council representatives and scientists.

1. Introduction

This report presents the results of the activities conducted in WP7, including desk research and an analysis of available literature as well as field research. The research team conducted an extensive literature review on existing policies and national initiatives across Europe in the areas of Open Science (OS) and gender issues in research and academia. An overview at an EU-level provided a background for further more in-depth analysis of policies and initiatives in open peer review (OPR), innovative dissemination, and alternative impact measurements - the project's key topics. The in-depth analysis was varied out for eight selected countries: Austria, Germany, Greece, Italy, Lithuania, Switzerland, the Netherlands and the United

Kingdom. The countries were selected considering different regions of Europe and different levels of uptake of OS policies and initiatives.

The literature review and policy mapping laid the foundation for further fieldwork. First of all, the country overviews were reviewed by project partners of OpenUP consortium. They validated the existing information and provided further inputs on what initiatives in OS, OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics are gaining momentum across the eight countries. The next stage of the fieldwork involved conducting semi-structured interviews with experts and stakeholders working in the key project areas as well as gender experts. The interviews focused on needs, requirements, and expectations concerning OPR, innovative dissemination and alternative metrics across the selected European countries, and on gender aspects within the European research system.

In total, 39 experts (22 of which were female and 17 were male) from a wide variety of stakeholder groups were brought into the conversation on these topics. The experts were identified through internet searchers, via recommendations from partners of OpenUP and by snowballing. Among the respondents were representatives of research performing institutions (universities and institutes), research funders, publishers, representatives of scientific libraries, infrastructure providers, and policymakers. Some of the interviewees held operative positions, while others reported managerial or senior roles. A more detailed overview of the interviewed stakeholders is presented in Table 2.

The interview programme consisted of two phases: firstly, the research team carried out 29 interviews with national experts from different fields using a detailed semi-structured questionnaire, which can be found in section 7.1. Secondly, we conducted 10 interviews with gender experts based on another semi-structured questionnaire, which can be found in section 7.2. Out of 29 national experts, 13 were female and 16 male. Additionally, among 10 gender experts, 9 were female and 1 male.

Table 2. Overview of the interviewed stakeholders.

Stakeholder group	Number of stakeholders	Geographic coverage
NATIONAL EXPERTS		
Scientific library	1	Austria
Researcher/Academia	2	Austria
Service provider	1	Austria
Research Funder	1	Austria
Researcher/Academia	2	Germany
Journal	1	Germany
Scientific Library	1	Greece
Scientific Library	1	Italy
Researcher/Academia	1	Italy
Scientific Library	2	Lithuania
Research Funder/Policy maker	2	Lithuania
Journal	1	Lithuania
Policy maker	1	Lithuania
Scientific Library	1	Netherlands
Scientific Society	1	Switzerland
Journal	1	Switzerland
Researcher/Academia	1	Based in Switzerland/international scope
Research Funder	3	United Kingdom
Service Provider	1	United Kingdom
Researcher/Academia	1	United Kingdom
Service Provider	1	United Kingdom
Policy maker	2	United Kingdom
GENDER EXPERTS		
Scientific society	1	Switzerland
Journal	2	United Kingdom
Researcher/Academia	1	Sweden
Researcher/Academia	1	Netherlands

Research Funder	1	Based in the Netherlands/international scope
Researcher/Academia	1	Greece
Research publisher	1	Based in the United States/international scope
Service provider	1	Based in the Netherlands/international scope
Service provider	1	Based in the United Kingdom/international scope

The interviews had two main purposes. Firstly, to validate our initial findings on OS related policies and initiatives at national levels. Therefore, the interviewees were selected by considering not only their area of expertise but also the country they work in. In addition, when carrying out interviews the research team gathered data on respondents' perceptions on OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics in general but also focused particularly the national level initiatives. The interviews with gender experts were directed towards identifying specific problems related to gender in research and academia and what role OS practices could play in offering solutions.

The interviews were carried out in person (when possible), in writing, and via telephone or Skype. They were recorded upon permission of the respondent and transcribed. The transcribed material was then analysed by qualitative content analysis using coding frames that largely corresponded with the interview questionnaires (see Annex 1).¹

Inputs from the interviews fed directly into the preparation of the OS issues overview and policy mapping. The interviews were particularly useful in identifying various initiatives at national level in the three topics of the OpenUP project and in the eight selected countries. The findings will also be directly incorporated into the final set of OpenUP's policy recommendations, which will support evaluating the need for and prioritisation of supportive actions for advancing a more open and gender-sensitive science system.

The researchers took the opportunity for direct interaction with the respondents, informed them about the goals of our project and invited them to get involved in the OpenUP activities, such as the upcoming policy workshop that will be held in May, 2018. This workshop will present OpenUP's policy recommendations to national stakeholders and policymakers and conduct their validation.

2. European Commission's priorities for Open Science

Open Science represents a shift in the current practices of research organisation and execution. Open Source, Open Access and Open Data are a few of the Open Science practices increasingly being taken up by researchers. These new practices are changing scientific work, transforming what are often closed and inaccessible legacy systems and processes to more open, transparent and collaborative ones.

A number of international policy initiatives contributed to the uptake of OS and OA policies in Europe in the 2000s. In the area of OA to publications, notable statements include the Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002)², the Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing (2003)³ and the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities (2003), as well as the Brussels Declaration on Open Access (2003)⁴. These initiatives called for a removal of barriers (fees, licensing restrictions, and copyright) to information and a wider uptake of OA approach to publicly funded research.

A significant step towards Open Access was made by the members of Science Europe, who unanimously adopted a set of 'Common Principles on the Transition to Open Access to Research Publications' (2013).⁵

¹ Schreier, M. (2012). *Qualitative Content Analysis in Practice*. London: Sage.

² <http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/>

³ <http://legacy.earlham.edu/~peters/fos/bethesda.htm>

⁴ <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>

⁵ <http://www.scienceeurope.org/policy/working-groups/open-access-to-scientific-publications/>

For the first time, the major European public Research Funding and Performing Organisations collectively endorsed and committed to actionable principles that will contribute to adoption of Open Access practices in research.

The European Commission (EC) is committed to removing currently existing barriers in accessing research results and promoting practices that comply with Open Science principles. The draft European Open Science Agenda⁶ defines five lines of policy intervention in the area:

- *Foster Open Science*, including raising awareness and supporting take-up of good/best Open Science practices and providing incentives to make scientific work openly available as early as possible;
- *Remove barriers to Open Science*. This includes among other issues, a review of possibilities to reward researchers for engaging in Open Science, promotion of discussion on research evaluation criteria (including altmetrics) and experimentation with more open peer review.
- *Development of research infrastructures for Open Science* calls for the creation of a European Open Science Cloud that would federate the existing data infrastructures and provide coordination at EU level and develop a plan for long-term preservation of research data.
- Mainstreaming and further promotion of open access policies to research data and research publications;
- *Embedding Open Science in society* to foster stronger relation between science and society as well as science and business actors to accelerate innovation.

The EC has started several initiatives in order to implement the action lines defined in the Draft European Open Science Agenda. The *Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP)*⁷ was assembled to investigate a range of Open Science aspects and to develop recommendations and guidelines on OS uptake for different stakeholders. The *European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*⁸ aspires to put order into the diverse and somewhat fragmented research infrastructure landscape across Europe. It aims to develop a virtual environment for European researchers to store, manage, analyse and re-use data.⁹ The *Expert Group on Altmetrics*¹⁰ was established to develop an agenda for a widely accepted responsible metric framework for all research outputs to be promoted to European countries, funders and institutions. Their published report on next-generation metrics presents the group's findings on the state-of-the-art of altmetrics and provides recommendations to the EC policymakers, research funders and other stakeholders based on the European Open Science Agenda.¹¹

The European Commission established two Working Groups and is in the process of assembling two expert groups that will address Open Science related issues:

⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/draft_european_open_science_agenda.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none

⁷ Open Science Policy Platform <http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-policy-platform>

⁸ European Open Science Cloud <http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-cloud>

⁹ European Commission, *Realising the European Open Science Cloud. First Report and Recommendations of the Commission High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud*, 2016, https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/realising_the_european_open_science_cloud_2016.pdf.

¹⁰ Open Science Policy Platforms expert group on altmetrics http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=altmetrics_eg

¹¹ European Commission, "Next-Generation Metrics: Responsible Metrics and Evaluation for Open Science," 2017, <http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/report.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none>.

- *Working Group on Rewards under Open Science* was created with the mandate to make recommendations in order that all researchers in Europe are recognised and rewarded for practising Open Science.¹² Their recently published report presents the limitations of the current recognition and reward process in academia and gives suggestions how these could be overcome and what new processes could be adopted. The report provides Open Science Career Assessment Matrix (OS-CAM) as a comprehensive approach to researcher assessment and briefly analyses how the European Research Area partnership policies and OS can be promoted through the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R).
- *Working Group on Education and Skills under Open Science* outlined key recommendations to enhance OS skills in the research community in their report.¹³ These recommendations are based on a survey that the working group carried out among researchers to assess the levels of awareness of OS policies and skills and facilities needed to practice OS. The report also outlines a European Skills and Qualifications Matrix for Open Science highlighting the importance of introducing and integrating (accredited) skills training for researchers at all career stages.
- *Horizon 2020 expert group on Future of Scholarly Publishing and Scholarly Communication (E03463)* will assess emerging and alternative open access business models with the aim of establishing how an economically viable transition towards open access can be achieved.¹⁴
- *Horizon 2020 Commission expert group on Turning FAIR Data into Reality* will produce recommendations on how to operationalise and facilitate the transition to make FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable/ re-producible) data sharing a default for scientific research by 2020.¹⁵

In addition, structural funds and EU-funded research activities directly target OS related issues. European research and e-infrastructure projects (e.g. the DRIVER projects, MedOANet, FOSTER, PASTEUR4OA, OpenAIRE, HIRMEOS) study Open Access, Open Data Management and other topics relevant for OS and provide systematic overviews of the OS issues across the EU and beyond. Some of those projects also provide recommendations how to further strengthen the uptake of OS.

The EC accelerated OA promotion by introducing a requirement for OA to publications and to research data in the EU's largest research funding programme Horizon 2020 (H2020), building on an Open Access Pilot which was introduced in the 7th Framework Programme (FP7). In H2020, OA to peer reviewed scientific publications is mandatory and both 'Gold' and 'Green' OA models are allowed.¹⁶ For Gold OA, costs charged to researchers by the publisher (Article Processing Charges, or APCs) are eligible for reimbursement. For Green OA, researchers must ensure OA to publications within six months (12 months for social sciences and humanities).

¹² European Commission, DG RTD, 2017. Evaluation of Research Careers fully acknowledging Open Science practices. Rewards, incentives and/or recognition for researchers practicing Open Science. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

¹³ European Commission, DG RTD, 2017. Providing researchers with the skills and competencies they need to practise Open Science. Open Science Skills Working Group Report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

¹⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3463>

¹⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetail&groupID=3464>

¹⁶ European Commission, DG RTD, "H2020 Programme. Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020" 2016, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf.

Regarding OA to research data, in 2014 the Commission introduced an Open Research Data Pilot in its research-funding programme Horizon 2020.¹⁷ The pilot¹⁸ aims to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by H2020 projects, taking into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and intellectual property rights, privacy concerns and security, as well as data management and preservation questions. Almost two thirds of the projects funded in 2015 openly shared their data. From 2017, the pilot was extended to all of the thematic areas of the programme. Currently, projects have to open their data by default with a possibility to opt out by providing justification.

The EC initiatives focus on various aspects of OS, including OA, Open Data and infrastructures for publications and data management that are more defined in terms of policy directions. The initiatives the EC is leading in these areas will enable the European science to adapt to the changing modus operandi of the research landscape and to switch to better scientific practices. Other topics, such as evaluation of researchers or peer review of scientific publication are also acknowledged in various documents as well as expert group work. However, the latter topics are still at a level of discussions among the scientific communities and more investigation is needed to fully integrate them in the research processes.

3. National policies and initiatives related to Open Science in Europe

In 2012, the European Commission issued a recommendation for Member States to define clear policies for dissemination of and OA to scientific publications and research data generated from public funds.¹⁹ In line with the recommendation, a later Commission's report outlined the current situation across the Member States, Norway and Turkey in regards to policies on OA to scientific publications and research data.²⁰ By combining data from the reports, from OpenAIRE National Open Access Desks²¹ and EUDAT's Data Access and Reuse Policies Working Group Workshop report²² we have collected a non-exhaustive list of national OA and Research Data Management (RDM) systems and their capacities in the EU-28, Norway and Switzerland (see Table 3).

Table 3. Overview of key OA and RDM initiatives at national level.

Country	Preferred type of open access (green, gold, both)	Overall level of policies on RDM*	Key national projects and initiatives (non-exhaustive selection of key initiatives)
Austria	Gold	Medium	Open Access Network Austria (OANA) e-Infrastructures Austria Digital Humanities Austria (DHA) Vienna Principles
Belgium	Green	Medium	Brussels Declaration on Open Access Liège model
Bulgaria	Both	N/A	No information on major OA initiatives found

¹⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/research/press/2016/pdf/opendata-infographic_072016.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none

¹⁸ Although it is mandatory (with opt-out) now it is still called Open Research Data Pilot.

¹⁹ European Commission, "Commission Recommendation of 17.7.2012 on Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information. C(2012) 4890 Final," 2012, https://ec.europa.eu/research/science-society/document_library/pdf_06/recommendation-access-and-preservation-scientific-information_en.pdf.

²⁰ European Commission, DG RTD, *Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information in Europe Report on the Implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 Final* (Brussels: European Commission, 2015), http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/openaccess/npr_report.pdf.

²¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/member-states-overview>

²² <https://www.eudat.eu/data-access-and-reuse-policies-darup>

Croatia	Both	Medium	SERSCIDA – Support for Establishment of National/Regional Social Sciences Data National OA journal platform Hrčak
Cyprus	Green	Low	National policy for Open Access in Cyprus (as of February 2016) Signing of a nationwide subscription contract between the Cyprus Academic Library Consortium (CALC) and BMC (Biomed Central)
Czech Republic	Both	Medium	No information on major OA initiatives found
Denmark	Green	Advanced	National Open Access Strategy (as of June 2014) Detailed monitoring of OA publications produced by the Danish Universities National Research Data Management Project OA Monitor project
Estonia	Green	Medium	Estonian Research Information System (ETIS)
Finland	Both	Advanced	Beneficiaries funded under the Academy of Finland are required to commit to open access publishing Open Science and Research Initiative (ATT) for the years 2014-2017
France	Both	Advanced	Revues.org platform Publishers' deposit policies Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETD) The Couperin consortium HAL open archive
Germany	Both	Advanced	Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities Information platform open-access.net OA-Network Open APC / INTACT project DINI working group, DINI certificate, several related projects
Greece	Green	N/A	ePublishing infrastructure for open access publications the Greek portal on Open Access
Hungary	Gold	Medium	HUNOR (HUNGarian Open Repositories) consortium
Ireland	Green	Advanced	Open Access to Irish Research Project, National Policy on Open Access (2012) NDLR (National Digital Learning Repository) RISE Group (Research Information Systems Exchange) DART-Europe
Italy	Both	Medium	Messina Declaration signed by Italian university and research organisations to support the OA Berlin declaration Conference of Italian Universities Rectors (CRUI) OA Working Group Portal for Italian Electronic Scholarly Literature in Institutional Archives (PLEIADI) Law 112/2013 that requires OA to research results publicly funded (green and gold road)
Latvia	Both	Low	No information on major OA initiatives found
Lithuania	Green	Advanced	Article 45 of the 2009 Law on Higher Education and Research of the Republic of Lithuania (adopted on April 30, 2009 and took effect on May 12, 2009) requires the results of scientific activity to be made publicly available As of February 2016, the Research Council of Lithuania adopted Guidelines for Open Access to Research Results
Luxembourg	Both	Low	Open Access initiative launched by the University of Luxembourg in collaboration with the University of Liège. ORBilu digital repository
Malta	Green	Low	No information on major OA initiatives found
Netherlands	Gold	Advanced	A number of university-led initiatives (esp. Erasmus University Rotterdam, Delft University of Technology, Twente and Utrecht University) The Secretary of State for Education, Culture and Science aims to have 100% of publications in OA by 2024 Representatives from Dutch scientific and government organizations created the National Plan Open Science The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO) has a mandate for OA publications
Norway	Green	Advanced	Norwegian Open Research Archives (NORA)
Poland	Both	Low	Conference of Rectors of Academic Schools in Poland 2012 Call for a national Open Access Mandate for research in Poland Kierunki rozwoju otwartego dostępu do treści naukowych w Polsce (a policy document which sets specific OA recommendations for all major stakeholders in Poland)

Portugal	Green	Medium	RepositóriUM Conference of Rectors of the Portuguese Universities Declaration on Open Access RCAAP (Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal = Portugal Open Access Science Repository) Open Access Policy Kit
Romania	Gold	Medium	No information on major OA initiatives found
Slovakia	Green	Medium	No information on major OA initiatives found
Slovenia	Both	Advanced	Resolution on Research and Innovation Strategy of Slovenia 2011-2020 National Strategy of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Slovenia 2015-2020 CLARIN.SI SI-DIH DARIAH
Spain	Green	N/A	RECOLECTA Research Group “acceso abierto a la ciencia” e-ciencia Consorcio Madroño
Sweden	Gold	Medium	OpenAccess.se programme SwePub DiVA consortium
Switzerland	Both	Medium	The SNSF - Swiss National Science Foundation has Open Access and Open Data in its Research Policy Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences (SAGW) sponsored journals 2017, National Open Access Strategy for Switzerland was adopted by the plenary assembly of swissuniversities ²³ Zenodo repository launched in 2013 by OpenAIRE and hosted at CERN OAK Open Archive holds published research output of Novartis Institutes for Biomedical Research (NIBR) and Novartis Corporate Research available for Open Access Between 2004 and 2006, the Berlin Declaration was signed by 12 Swiss research institutions and by 4 academic governing bodies including the Rector's Conference of the Swiss Universities, the Conference of the Swiss Universities of Applied Sciences, the Swiss Conference of Schools for Teacher Education and the Council of the Swiss Scientific Academies.
United Kingdom	Gold	Advanced	Digital Curation Centre: training, guidance and consultancy on RDM and sharing SHERPA: Securing a Hybrid Environment for Research Preservation and Access OAPEN-UK Collaborative R&D on OA Monograph Jisc Research at Risk R&D programme, including Research Data Spring UKCORR UK Council of Research Repositories

Source: National Open Access Desks, OpenAIRE <https://www.openaire.eu/member-states-overview>; European Commission (2015). EUDAT Data Access and Reuse Policies Working Group Workshop report <https://www.eudat.eu/data-access-and-reuse-policies-darup>. *categorisation adapted from: Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information in Europe. Report on the implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 final;

Based on our initial review some of the EU-15 countries (especially Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Sweden, Switzerland, and the UK) were key contributors to the development of OA policy. In most of these countries, publicly funded research projects are encouraged to commit to OA publishing. More recent developments in Cyprus, Lithuania, Italy, Finland and Denmark point to the creation of new or a reinforcement of existing OA policies and legal frameworks. While these developments indicate an overall improvement, OA policies remained at a more nascent stage in many EU-13 countries (e.g. Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Romania, Slovakia) and some countries in South Europe (e.g. Greece) and the EU-15 (e.g. Luxembourg).

Based on the National Open Access Desks data, in the Czech Republic, there was no official government policy or mandate to deposit research output arising from grants, nor were there universities which have made institutional commitments to a mandatory OA policy to deposit published journal articles. In Italy,

²³ <http://www.library.ethz.ch/en/ms/Open-Access-at-ETH-Zurich/News/National-open-access-strategy-for-Switzerland>, https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Komm/MeMi/PR_SWU_national_strategy_Open_Access_20170201_EN.pdf

the awareness of OA and RDM remained at an early stage due to the lack of a national strategic framework and legislation, although relevant actions were made in 2016 to change the national copyright law in line with the changes made previously in other countries, notably Germany, the Netherlands and France.

Table 4 shows further data on the OA and RDM capacities at the national level in terms of operating OA repositories, OA journals and open research data repositories. Overall, the number of items in each category tends to correlate with country size and public R&D expenditure levels. The UK, Germany, France, Italy and Spain had the largest numbers of operating OA repositories and journals. However, a large number of open research data repositories is operated in only two of these countries (i.e. Germany and the UK). This indicates an overall trend across the EU whereby virtually all EU countries possessed an advanced infrastructure for OA journals. However, most countries had a low number of operating open research data repositories.

Table 4. OA and RDM capacities at national level.

Country	Number of operating OA repositories (source: www.opendoar.org)	Number of OA journals (source: https://doaj.org/ ; Directory of Open Access Journals)	Number of open research data repositories (source: https://www.re3data.org/)
Austria	28	46	28
Belgium	23	31	27
Bulgaria	7	38	No data/open research data repositories found
Croatia	21	89	No data/open research data repositories found
Cyprus	4	5	1
Czech Republic	16	85	7
Denmark	12	26	18
Estonia	6	18	5
Finland	16	26	9
France	118	160	81
Germany	194	351	261
Greece	34	30	9
Hungary	33	27	5
Ireland	22	14	9
Israel	No data/OA repositories found	6	6
Italy	110	291	28
Latvia	3	9	No data/open research data repositories found
Lithuania	11	34	4
Luxembourg	4	2	5
Malta	1	2	No data/open research data repositories found
Netherlands	34	147	39
Norway	52	51	17
Poland	90	392	4
Portugal	49	70	2
Romania	3	289	2
Slovakia	No data/OA repositories found	43	1
Slovenia	10	49	3
Spain	123	514	15
Sweden	42	64	18
Switzerland	17	234	48
United Kingdom	249	765	238

Source: compiled by the authors using OpenDOAR, DOAJ and re3data data.

4. Changing the research landscape: initiatives in open peer review, innovative dissemination and altmetrics

Exponential growth of research outputs and an increasing demand for more open, transparent and reproducible science has been pushing stakeholders (including researchers, publishers, funders, institutions and industry) to re-think how research results are published, evaluated and assessed. Traditional ways of publication and evaluation do not correspond to this changing landscape and require new practices and policies for the review-disseminate-assess cycle of research. Open Access and other Open Science components accompanied by technological developments are changing the practices of stakeholders involved in academic research. In addition, innovative tools to disseminate research have altered how and to whom science is communicated, and how the public interacts with the scientific community.

Stakeholders and experts interviewed for our field research agreed that the traditional cycle of *review-disseminate-assess* is no longer suitable for current academic research. Many respondents predict that OA will be mainstream by 2020 due to its many advantages, although they disagree on how the transition to OA should be implemented. A group of interviewees supported the mechanisms that demand making all state-funded research openly available. Some of them went even further arguing that a similar policy should also apply to the sharing of data, highlighting fields like biomedical sciences, where it is crucial to publish as much incremental findings or negative results as possible. However, other interviewees preferred a more transitional approach. According to them, while OA should be encouraged and supported, it is essential not to force it. Researchers should be educated, trained and provided with funding for OA. Their involvement in shaping the transition of the ecosystem would foster the change in the scientific culture and could then reinforce the adoption of OA and other OS practices.

General resistance against Open Science, nonetheless, exists in scientific communities. Most of the interviewed stakeholders from researcher/academia group stated that they still feel tied up with the traditional system, because their research, funding and ultimately their entire career paths depend on it. In many cases this is due to the lack of understanding on how Open Science works and is financed, and not knowing why it could be beneficial. This leads to a general sense of confusion, fear and even indifference in the context of OS issues.

These factors contribute to inertia, which constitute one of the biggest reasons behind the inactivity among stakeholders in the context of OA and OS promotion. Interests of publishers also add to this inertia, because they rely on the profits from the established business models. Some research shows that redirecting journal subscription fees to OA publishing services could significantly reduce the publishers' profits.²⁴ Hence, publishers are often unwilling to change the status quo.

Further sections of this report present desk research and interview data and analyse how the emerging OS practices, including open peer review, innovative dissemination and altmetrics can contribute to the changing research landscape. The overview also includes some findings from the OpenUP survey, although they are discussed in more detail in other deliverables of the project.²⁵

²⁴ Schimmer, R., Geschuhn, K. K., & Vogler, A. (2015). Disrupting the subscription journals' business model for the necessary large-scale transformation to open access.

<http://pubman.mpdl.mpg.de/pubman/faces/viewItemOverviewPage.jspx?itemId=escidoc:2148961>

²⁵ See Görögh, E., et al. (2017). Deliverable D3.1 – Practices, evaluation and mapping: Methods, tools and user needs. OpenUP project; Kraker, P., Bachleitner, R., et al. (2017). Deliverable D4.1 – Practices evaluation and mapping: Methods, tools and user needs. OpenUP project. http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUP_D4.1_Practices-evaluation-and-

4.1 Open peer review

The traditional peer review process used by many scientific journals is subject to criticism on several fronts.²⁶ For example, the publishers or editors can choose the reviewers confidentially. Also the review process and reviews themselves are not known to the public. It is also often described as unreliable, too lengthy, biased and lacking accountability and transparency.²⁷ OPR, on the other hand, opens up the traditional process in order to help to address these issues.

Open peer review makes the traditional process more open and transparent by introducing such aspects as open identities (author and reviewer disclose their identities), open reports (review reports are published along the publication) and open participation (wider participation of interested parties in the process).²⁸ These new aspects enable a more open discussion around research outputs. OPR can also help authors get feedback not only on the final research outputs (articles or books) but also on what is created at different stages of the research process (software codes or datasets). Moreover, OPR can engage a larger number of reviewers in delivering scientific reviews.

Various initiatives are emerging among researchers who are willing to employ OPR. For example, the Open Science Peer Review Oath²⁹ includes four principles³⁰ that are in line with OPR practices. Reviewers are encouraged to add a link to the oath and to inform the authors and potential publishers that the reviewer will work following the principles set out in the oath. The COPE Ethical Guidelines for Peer Reviewers³¹ outlined by the Committee on Publication Ethics set out the basic principles and standards to which all peer reviewers should adhere to during the peer review process. Also, alternatives to the traditional closed peer review process are already offered by a number of OA journals and publication platforms (Frontiers, BMJ and F1000research). Frontiers, for example, are using a collaborative review process that also includes an Interactive Review phase. In this phase, authors and reviewers can interact with each other through real-time comments in the discussion forum.³²

However, there is a number of obstacles that still hinder a wider adoption of these novel practices. Despite being a major pillar of Open Science, OPR does not have a standardised definition or a common set of features and implementations.³³ A majority of the interviewees were familiar with different aspects of OPR, however they argued that the lack of developments in the area resulted in a common misconception among the researcher community, particularly those who are still not aware of different forms of OPR, that OPR is not as rigorous compared to the traditional peer review.

mapping-Methods-tools-and-user-needs.pdf; Gauch, S., and Blümel, C. 2016. Deliverable D5.1 – Altmetrics Status Quo. Project OpenUP. EC HLEG Report on Altmetrics, <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/report.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none>

²⁶ See Görögh, E., et al. (2017).

²⁷ Lee, C. J., Sugimoto, C. R., Zhang, G. and Cronin, B. (2013), Bias in peer review. *J Am Soc Inf Sci Tec*, 64: 2–17.

doi:10.1002/asi.22784; Manchikanti, L., Kaye, A. D., Boswell, M and Hirsch, J. A. 2015. Medical Journal Peer Review: Process and Bias. *Pain Physician*, vol. 18, pp: E1-E14.

²⁸ European Commission, “Validation of the Results of the Public Consultation on Science 2.0: Science in Transition,” 2015, http://ec.europa.eu/research/consultations/science-2.0/science_2_0_final_report.pdf#view=fit&pagemode=none.

²⁹ Jelena Aleksic et al., “An Open Science Peer Review Oath,” *F1000Research*, January 9, 2015, doi:10.12688/f1000research.5686.2.

³⁰ Principle 1: I will sign my name to my review; Principle 2: I will review with integrity; Principle 3: I will treat the review as a discourse with you; in particular, I will provide constructive criticism; Principle 4: I will be an ambassador for the practice of open science

³¹ http://publicationethics.org/files/Ethical_guidelines_for_peer_reviewers_0.pdf

³² <http://home.frontiersin.org/about/review-system>

³³ <https://f1000research.com/articles/6-588/v2>

Hesitance to adopt OPR practices is also reflected in the OpenUP survey results. We asked the survey respondents which option of open peer review they would prefer for their own research outputs, either a more open peer review or the established peer review process (See figure below). The answers showed that in some categories there was no unanimous preference among the researchers. For instance, 42% of researchers preferred open participation (when a wider community of the researchers contribute to peer review) and 41% supported closed participation (only appointed peer reviewers contribute to peer review). Also, small differences were noted among the researchers who ‘strongly supported’ or ‘supported’ open report (review report is published alongside the relevant article), and closed report (no review report is published alongside the relevant article), and who assigned open pre-review (manuscripts are made available to researchers/public before formal peer review), and ‘no open pre-review’ (manuscripts are not made available to researchers/public before formal peer review) to the same categories.

Still, there were some similarities of opinions. Nearly 30% more respondents preferred closed identity (when neither the author’s nor the reviewer’s identity are disclosed) than open identity (59% versus 29%). Majority of researchers (over 70% of the surveyed researchers) supported peer review of data that underlie a scientific publication. Although it is implemented by some journals, it is not yet a widespread practice.

Figure 1. Proportions of respondents attributing their support to different peer-review approaches.

Note: Responses to question ‘2.1c - Which of the following peer review approaches would you choose to undergo for your own research outputs?’ N= [855 - 915]. The full data set and the questionnaire are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.556157>.

Supporters of OPR, which included researchers, representatives of scientific libraries and journal editors throughout the interviews, agreed that a diverse approach to peer review, which refers to flexibility in terms of adopting open identities, open reports and open participation, is needed. They indicated that a number of researchers, especially young researchers, fear retaliation from their colleagues, who are usually in more senior positions, or are more established researchers. Therefore, the younger researchers might be unwilling to disclose their identities while conducting a review.

A half of interview respondents argued that neither open nor traditional peer review would be appropriate if adopted as a fixed solution. Instead, a more diverse approach is needed. They agreed that non-anonymity

should be encouraged and fostered, but they also tended to argue that there are cases where an option for anonymity is necessary. Along with the adoption of OPR, they proposed to introduce an option for double or triple blind review (where author identities are not known to either reviewers or the editor, and reviewers are not known to authors), which would allow flexibility in terms of making one's identity open. Moreover, they emphasized that it is essential to present the involved parties with advantages and disadvantages of every option. Many highlighted that these options would require different strategies to mitigate biases related to gender, career stage, geographic and enterprise size, which affect the current peer review process.

A better-quality assessment procedure that would demand more responsible reviews is also needed. The interviewed researchers expressed being generally overwhelmed by the large number of requests for reviews as well as being pressured to write them well. Some reported that under such circumstances, they opt for writing the reviews while relying on the fact that the review will not be made publicly available. In such a way, even if their reviews are unsubstantial or hostile, the reviews are not revealed publicly and therefore their reputation cannot be harmed. Introducing a certain element of transparency could help to not only address these situations, and thus improve the quality of reviews overall, but also assist in recognizing fraudulent reviews. According to a group of interviewees, this element of transparency could be introduced by funders asking to publish reviews alongside the publications, especially if these publications are publicly funded.

A system of incentives and credits could foster further adoption of OPR practices. Many interviewees reported that they had never engaged in OPR due to a lack of resources and credit for their efforts. However, they stated that if reviews were uniquely attached to their authors, they could be cited or included in CV and grant application, this would allow them to reconsider OPR. Therefore, allowing researchers to be acknowledged for their efforts, for instance, with the use of a unique identifier (e.g. ORCID) might make it more appealing to invest the additional time and resources needed to advance OPR uptake.

Interview data showed a division of opinions on whether it is the time to encourage the adoption of OPR practices and how these should be implemented. Approximately 70% of the interviewees emphasized that it is essential to fund and promote studies as well as to advertise successful examples in the context of OPR to identify best practices. Additional experimental experience and training of researchers on how to handle negative opinions as well as new methods for applying better language in reviews could also progress the adoption of OPR. However, not everyone agreed that the political process should be triggered yet to enforce changes to OPR. Around 10% of respondents representing service providers and open access and open data advocates among policymakers insisted that it is still too early to propose any policy changes to the peer review system, as it could come at a price of successfully delivering on OA and RDM, which currently feature in most of the high-level conversations.

4.2 Innovative dissemination

The European Commission envisions Open Science as an innovative way of spreading scientific knowledge and making it open to the public free of charge. Essential to this vision are novel ways of producing and disseminating knowledge. Until recently, research dissemination has often implied a one-way communication from researchers to the society, or was directed only towards other academics. This is changing and currently most of the research funders, including the EC, are calling for stronger engagement

of policy makers, industry, civil society organisations and citizens.³⁴ The engagement of different stakeholders in research and innovation is thought to foster mutual understanding, co-create research and innovation outcomes, and provide input into policy agendas. However, a number of limitations inherent to various scientific communities and institutional cultures still limit the uptake of innovative dissemination methods.

In OpenUP, innovative dissemination is defined as dissemination that goes beyond traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books, and monographs), conferences and workshops. For example, it can include such tools as blogging, social media and videos. It can target academia or broader audiences and facilitate research result uptake and understanding. More specific examples of innovative dissemination used by research projects are outlined in one of the OpenUP deliverables.³⁵

To support the beneficiaries of EC grants in their research communication efforts, the Commission provides toolkits on research communication. “Communicating EU Research and Innovation - A Guide for Project Participants” outlines the main steps that researchers, who participate in framework programmes, need to take to define their research communication strategy and its implementation.³⁶ Another guide “Communicating research for evidence-based policymaking” is directed towards researchers in socio-economic sciences and the humanities.³⁷ It aims to help them plan and produce policy recommendations and engage policy makers.

These two documents outline overall communication strategies for European research projects. The innovative dissemination approaches in both of these documents are seen as one part of the overall science communication and promotion strategies. This is also the case in research communication practices in the eight countries analysed in this report (see section 5). Researchers across Europe, who receive funding from various national and international funding agencies, are advised and trained on how to communicate their work by also including the use of innovative dissemination tools (particularly social media).

The OpenUP survey showed that the use of innovative dissemination channels among researchers in Europe is not widespread. The data showed that researchers mostly use traditional methods (peer-reviewed research publications) when disseminating their own research (see figure below). Whereas almost all researchers reported using academic publishing, conferences and workshops, only about a third reported engaging in event for the general public or target audiences other than researchers. From interviews we established that respondents were broadly familiar with the concept of innovative dissemination, but due to a lack of extensive knowledge about it or actual use of such methods, their feedback in this area was limited compared to the topics of OPR and altmetrics.

³⁴ European Commission, “Responsible Research and Innovation: Research and Innovation Europe’s Ability to Respond to Societal Challenges,” 2012, https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_public_engagement/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf. Also see: <https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/index.cfm?pg=policy&lib=engagement>

³⁵ See Kraker, P. et al. (2017).

³⁶ European Commission, *Communicating EU Research & Innovation – A Guide for Project Participants* (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2012), doi:10.2777/7985.

³⁷ European Commission, *Communicating Research for Evidence-Based Policymaking. A Practical Guide for Researchers in Socio-Economic Sciences and Humanities* (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2010), doi: 10.2777/9276.

Figure 2. Proportions of researchers frequently using listed dissemination channels to disseminate their own research.

Note: Responses to questions 3.5 and 3.6 of OpenUP Survey. The full data set and the questionnaire are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.556157>.

“3.5 - Which of these channels listed do you use most frequently to disseminate your own research to reach your target groups?” N= [855 – 955]. “3.6 - And how frequently do you use these sources to inform your professional work as a researcher?” N= [864 – 956]. The percentages show a share of respondents who chose “Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)” and “Most of the time (60-89% of the time)” answer categories.

Interview respondents attributed the low uptake of innovative dissemination methods in research communities to a number of limitations that are inherent to current scientific communities and institutional cultures. Many respondents reported that scientific communities resist adopting changes to current practices, a product of the conservatism that often prevails in the academic sector. There is also confusion regarding the question of who is responsible for making editorial decisions and initiating innovative dissemination processes within institutions. A lack of specifications from the funders on each stakeholder’s specific responsibilities contributes to this confusion. Additional issues arise from the fact that larger organisations, and researchers associated with them, have an advantage against individuals or smaller organisations in terms of capabilities (resources and access) to target larger audiences.

It is necessary to balance the way researchers use innovative dissemination methods. Some interviewees, including journal editors and policymakers, reported that it is important for institutions to strongly encourage or even mandate that scientists invest time in enabling the public to ask questions. This has been observed to have a significant impact in areas such as climate science. If institutions took a more proactive role in facilitating this process, scientists would still be able to focus on balancing the time invested in citizen engagement while also maintaining a primary focus on scientific discourse. A specific role of researchers, communication departments and the institutions in this context would have to be clearly defined. Other interviewees, however, highly criticised the idea of mandating researchers to disseminate in addition to his/her research work. They insisted that institutional cultures have to remain flexible and allow researchers to make a choice themselves on the means to communicate about their research to the public.

However, most of the interviewees agreed that it is overall very important to focus on making research reusable and producing material that small and medium size enterprises can use to contribute to increasing the impact of research. Therefore, it is seen as essential to not only produce excellent research but also find effective innovative dissemination channels to reach specific audiences. It also remains essential to find ways to produce research outputs, which can be available to people with disabilities. These issues have to be addressed to facilitate equal access to research for all.

Although the EC and national funders aim to make research more visible and impactful, a large majority of researchers still engage in traditional dissemination activities that have limited potential to reach the public and policy makers.³⁸ According to the interview respondents this restricted uptake of innovative dissemination methods mostly results from the resistance to change and the power of established traditions in scientific communities and institutional cultures.

4.3 Alternative metrics

Currently, bibliometric indicators like the h-index³⁹ or the Journal Impact Factor (JIF)⁴⁰ are used extensively in measuring and assessing research outputs. However, they receive significant criticism. The h-index is believed to have a bias towards senior researchers and JIF is said to reflect the overall impact of a journal and not that of a specific article.⁴¹ These and other bibliometric indicators are failing to prove their suitability for measuring research outputs and their impact, in the context of a movement towards Open Science. In response to this, altmetrics emerged to broaden the meaning of impact, which has revealed the need to redesign the system even further to fit the current needs of research assessment. The growing uptake of new forms of dissemination (e.g. blogs, Twitter, openly available reports and data) is now also driving the use of alternative metrics.⁴²

Due to the growing interest in the area of altmetrics, in 2016 the European Commission's DG Research and Innovation established an Expert Group with an aim to review the status quo of different altmetrics and to

³⁸ Kraker, P., et al. (2017).

³⁹ J. E. Hirsch, "An Index to Quantify an Individual's Scientific Research Output That Takes into Account the Effect of Multiple Coauthorship," *Scientometrics* 85, no. 3 (December 1, 2010): 741–54, doi:10.1007/s11192-010-0193-9.

⁴⁰ Eugene Garfield, "Citation Analysis as a Tool in Journal Evaluation," *Science* 178, no. 4060 (November 3, 1972): 471–79, doi:10.1126/science.178.4060.471.

⁴¹ "The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)," 2012, <http://www.ascb.org/dora/>; Diana Hicks et al., "Bibliometrics: The Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics," *Nature News* 520, no. 7548 (April 23, 2015): 429, doi:10.1038/520429a.

⁴² Gauch, S., and Blümel, C. (2016).

set up a framework for the responsible use of metrics, including altmetrics.⁴³ In March 2017, the Expert Group published the report that includes 12 recommendations.⁴⁴ The recommendations target the EC Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP), policy makers, funders and other stakeholders and are aligned with the European Open Science Agenda. The report acknowledges that all the current indicators have their advantages and flaws. Hence, the Expert Group calls for the responsible use of different metrics currently available (including altmetrics), considering transparency and openness. Reports prepared by Working Group on Rewards under Open Science and Working Group on Education and Skills under Open Science provide specific recommendations on how to enhance OS skills in the research community and include them into the academic reward and evaluation system for career development.⁴⁵

According to the EC Expert Group reports as well as the experts interviewed in context of OpenUP, alternative metrics hold the potential to improve the way research impact is understood and measured. They also have the potential to identify gaps in the researcher recognition, evaluation and researcher career advancement systems that have been previously overlooked. A majority of the interviewees valued altmetrics for measuring research impact faster. Many also positively viewed the possibility to indicate the impact of research outputs other than scientific publications. These include datasets, codes, “nano publication” (semantic publishing) and self-publishing (blogging, microblogging, comments/annotations on existing work).⁴⁶ Respondents reported that these alternative metrics are already widely used to count real downloads of research outputs that are mostly text-based, but more recently also across universities for research data as well. When used for research data, they help inform decisions around which types of data should be kept, depending on when it was last downloaded and how many real downloads occurred. By taking more elements of the research lifecycle into account and looking across different categories of actions, altmetrics allow for a much more comprehensive evaluation of research impact and researchers’ productivity levels.

Altmetrics are in rather early stages of development. It is still unclear what these new indicators exactly measure and how they can be applied in practice for research evaluation. Because of these reasons, some interviewees cautioned against employing altmetrics as a research evaluation method despite their many advantages. Some respondents argued that altmetrics depend too much on social media (whose uptake is low in some countries or disciplines) and can therefore produce new forms of competition among scientists, which could consequentially undermine the quality of scientific research.⁴⁷ Some were sceptical about the use of altmetrics as they take the effort to engage with a specific audience or how the audience engages with the content into account, but lacks depth (not a measure of depth of the engagement). As alternative metrics still lack robustness and largely depend on data providers that could limit access to that data, the system may be easily gamed.

However, there are already areas where these emerging measures bring positive change. Due to these early successful examples, most of the interviewed stakeholders agreed that there are areas where integrating new metrics with other bibliometric indicators could be useful. Some argued that when Google Scholar was introduced, it was a big step forward towards this, as it was one of the first alternative ways to measure impact. Many interview respondents valued this service compared to the capabilities of

⁴³ http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=altmetrics_eg

⁴⁴ European Commission, 2017. “Next-Generation Metrics: Responsible Metrics and Evaluation for Open Science.”

⁴⁵ European Commission, DG RTD, 2017. Evaluation of Research Careers fully acknowledging Open Science practices. Rewards, incentives and/or recognition for researchers practicing Open Science. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union; European Commission, DG RTD, 2017. Providing researchers with the skills and competencies they need to practise Open Science. Open Science Skills Working Group Report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

⁴⁶ Jason Priem et al., “Altmetrics: A Manifesto,” October 26, 2010, <http://altmetrics.org/manifesto/>.

⁴⁷ European Commission, 2017. “Next-Generation Metrics: Responsible Metrics and Evaluation for Open Science.”

traditional metrics, since Google Scholar could capture more citations, automatically track them and facilitate quicker search for citations in non-English texts.

There are also other experiments helping to progress thinking about these metrics, inform the understanding of the algorithms that count them and other aspects around the research process. For example, to help researchers tell data-driven stories about their work, Impact Story established a new scholarly reward system that values and encourages a web-native scholarship.⁴⁸ Sharing and comparison of statistics are also being promoted. IRIS UK, which is a standards-based statistics aggregation service for repositories in the UK, enables these processes with the use of COUNTER standard.⁴⁹ This service allows IRIS-UK to collect raw usage data from UK institutional repositories and process these data into COUNTER-compliant statistics. COUNTER has the Code of Practice that allows preselected publishers and vendors to report usage of their electronic resources in a consistent way. Therefore libraries, for example, can better recognise the value of electronic resources.⁵⁰

The University of Vienna is testing a new internal system, which generates bibliometric profiles for each professor according to individually relevant aspects and publication culture in the particular discipline where he works. These profiles gather a quantitative analysis of a researchers' publication output in three main categories, including activity, visibility and impact analysis in the last 10 years of every researcher's career.⁵¹ The analysis is based on publications indexed in leading international data sources such as the Web of Science Core Collection Citation Indexes, Scopus, Google Scholar and relevant subject specific databases. Additionally, interviewed stakeholders reported that Slovenia and Croatia have already tested altmetrics on a national level. In Slovenia for example, the number of views and downloads along with the link to a digital repository are now being shown for publications from Open Science Slovenia portal.⁵² Interviewees also suggested that if along with citations of research data, figures, and open reports of peer review, the results of alternative tracking were uniquely attached to their author, then altmetrics could also impact hiring decisions, tenure appointments and earning credits towards a grant.

Respondents noted, however, that citations and citation databases are generally not transparent, community governed or audible, which hinders the integrity of research and research evaluations. A number of risks for universities and funders emerge, which encourages costly purchase of near monopoly products, resulting in non-auditable allocation of funding and the delegitimised citation benchmarking metrics. These metrics refer to the indicators that describe output performance by comparing it with the average outputs within the same field or journal.⁵³ In response to this, JISC started to experiment with open citations in collaboration with the Open University. They initiated CORE, which is an aggregation of OA outputs from the UK and worldwide repositories and OA journals.⁵⁴ Using the core aggregations of OA outputs, which has a large number of text-based outputs, and by undertaking a semantic analysis of the citations, they are now able to identify the reasons behind citations and how close they are either in subject matter terms or peer terms. This allows to measure how any article contributes to the progress of scholarly discussion.

The way to further introduce altmetrics into the scientific discourse is still largely a contested topic. Some advocated a more forceful way of encouraging the use of altmetrics by the requirements from third-party

⁴⁸ <https://profiles.impactstory.org/about>

⁴⁹ <http://irus.mimas.ac.uk/support/supportmaterials>

⁵⁰ <https://www.projectcounter.org/about/>

⁵¹ http://bibliothek.univie.ac.at/bibliometrie/files/General_Information_about_Bibliometric_Profiles.pdf

⁵² <http://scimet.izum.si/en/altmetrics>

⁵³ <https://scholarlyfutures.jiscinvolve.org/wp/2016/06/towards-full-text-based-research-metrics-exploring-semantometrics/>

⁵⁴ <https://core.ac.uk/>

research funding grounds to track them. Others disagreed, stating that these new measures have to gradually become a part of the Open Science culture instead. These respondents emphasised that it is essential to centre efforts to introduce altmetrics and raise awareness about it. For instance by explaining what altmetrics stand for and developing a definition for researcher impact. This point of view was also reflected in the results of the OpenUP survey. Only a third of survey respondents were aware of the term altmetrics and an even smaller proportion reported to have used them in the past.⁵⁵ This indicates that there is a need for more awareness of altmetrics among the research community itself.

As traditional measures and indicators are failing to prove suitable for measuring research outputs and their impact, altmetrics can offer to broaden the meaning of impact and provide other approaches to research evaluation. They hold the potential to improve researcher recognition, evaluation and career advancement systems by identifying the levels of productivity on a more individual basis. A lot of limitations still hinder the wider use of altmetrics as they are still in early stages of development. Many interviewees agreed, however, that if implemented with a specific goal of achieving a socially-engaged OS system, along with investments in infrastructure, institutions, libraries and society, altmetrics could address problems associated with the lack of reliability and transparency inherent in traditional evaluation system.

4.4 Gender inequities in research

According to the *Gender in the Global Research Landscape* report published in 2017, there has been some progress towards gender equality in research and innovation, as there are more women in research globally than there has been in the previous decade. Women make up on average 41% of the researcher population in the EU-28, making the region one of the leaders in this regard.⁵⁶ However, women are still significantly underrepresented in a number of disciplines. In the scientific fields of Computer Science, Energy, Engineering, Mathematics, and Physics & Astronomy, the majority of countries and regions have fewer than 25% of women among researchers.⁵⁷ Moreover, women are still severely under-represented at the highest levels of the academic career path and in leadership positions. In terms of the EU-28, the largest gap is observed at the highest level of the academic career ladder, where women represented on average only 21% of Grade A staff.⁵⁸ This result revealed a 58% difference from men in the same category.⁵⁹

The Science, Technology, Engineering and Math (STEM) disciplines and leadership positions are critical areas for achieving success in gender balance across scientific communities. Gender imparity in these areas has a considerable impact on authorship and recognition of women, which also result in wide variations in the working conditions of female researchers, their career advancement and participation in academic decision-making.

⁵⁵ Blümel, C. (2017). D5.4 report on final taxonomy linking channels of dissemination and altmetrics. OpenUP project. <http://openup-h2020.eu/project-material/project-deliverables/>

⁵⁶ https://www.elsevier.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0008/265661/ElsevierGenderReport_final_for-web.pdf p.17

⁵⁷ Ibid, p.22

⁵⁸ Grade A represents the data for staff at the level corresponding to the rank of full professor in the majority of the countries, or otherwise representing the highest post at which research is normally conducted. Detailed explanation is available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/she_figures_2015-final.pdf p.130, whereas the She Figures report 2015, highlighting that women represented on average only 21% of Grade A staff is available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_gender_equality/she_figures_2015-final.pdf p.129

⁵⁹ Ibid, p.129

Through our desk research and interviews, we identified four areas relevant to the themes of the OpenUP project covering gender bias in:

- Publication peer review process;
- Editorial boards;
- Review panels;
- Research dissemination;
- Research and researcher evaluation.

In the sections 4.4.1. – 4.4.4, we present our findings from desk research and interviews in the areas above. Whereas desk research helped identify specific issues and provide an overview of the current situation, interviews with gender experts provided inputs on various practices and initiatives promoted nationally or by some researcher to improve gender equity in research and academia. In some of these areas, aspects of OS and responsible research and innovation (RRI) are important. For example, by making the peer review process more transparent or research dissemination more inclusive. However, some of these aspects also pose risks which are also outlined in the sections below.

4.4.1. Gender bias in the peer review process

One of the factors that contributes to gender inequality in academia is the gender bias associated with the peer review process. Since humans are susceptible to cognitive biases, unrelated to the merit of science, they affect the judgment of reviewers in peer reviews. Throughout the interviews, many respondents revealed that explicit and implicit biases threaten the objectivity of peer reviews, because knowing the gender of an author or reviewer of the paper impacts behaviour and how people conduct themselves. Many interviewees stated that this is favourable to men as more of them are invited to conduct peer reviews than women. Multiple studies confirmed that the attributes of referees, such as gender and region, can act as determinants of a referee's handling of manuscripts, particularly in terms of the number of manuscripts being reviewed, review time and rejection rate.⁶⁰

According to 40% of interview respondents across all stakeholder groups, open peer review may help to address gender bias in the current peer review process. For example, some of the interviewed researchers and journal editors suggested that through making the review reports and identities of reviewers openly available, it would be possible to expose gender bias. However, they also acknowledged that along with that, it would be necessary to introduce additional training elements for all stakeholders involved in managing editorial policy, selection of reviewers, instructions for reviewers, criteria for evaluation of research design and process, authorship order, who takes responsibility for errors, and other aspects of peer review process.

Interviewed publishers and editors recommended to combine OPR with additional implicit anti-bias training for researchers, editors and reviewers. Recognition of such bias can only be attained by increasing one's levels of self-awareness and equipping oneself with ways to manage them during the research process. Additionally, the interviewed stakeholders from the top-level positions acknowledged that they also lack training in the area of implicit anti-bias as the leaders, managers and personnel within publishing organisations, who frame training programmes for editors and reviewers.

Despite the lack of systematic anti-bias training, which was reported by most of the stakeholders, a few

⁶⁰ Grod, O. N., Budden, A. E., Tregenza, T., Koricheva, J., Leimu, R., Aarssen, L. W., & Lortie, C. J. (2008). Systematic Variation in Reviewer Practice According to Country and Gender in the Field of Ecology and Evolution. *PLoS ONE*, 3(9), e3202. <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0003202>

indicated that they have already been involved in individual activities that are aimed at teaching them more about stereotypes and exploring one's biases. Tools, like the Harvard implicit association test,⁶¹ have been effectively utilised for these purposes. To deepen the understanding of gender issues and its impact on scientific quality further, they recommended to showcase more diverse role models.

On the contrary, others argued that OPR could, in fact, escalate gender disparity in peer review. Researchers, particularly female, who are already in more vulnerable positions due to biases against their gender, might be considerably affected by the open identity aspect of the process.⁶² Additional factors such as young age or career stage may further compromise researchers' ability to reveal their identities openly due to fear of retaliation from more established scientists within their fields. Due to these reasons their reviews may not offer substantial criticism, especially when knowing that the author of the output under review, may be making hiring or tenure decisions and evaluating their grants in the future.

Due to these differences in opinions whether OPR would help to advance or hinder gender equality, further gathering and examination of empirical evidence should be encouraged. It might reveal the points at which biases arise and what the best way to address them would be. If more data in this area were available, it would also be possible to conduct detailed comparisons of how differently open peer review, double blind review and even triple blind review help to advance or hinder gender bias. Other specific areas that are still largely contested among researchers could be explored such as whether it matters that editors know the gender of the reviewers and authors, and if gender influences the quality of the review, as well as what aspects of the review process could be managed differently toward different effects.

4.4.2. Gender bias in editorial boards

The lack of information on gender diversity also constitutes another important factor contributing to the discrepancies among the researchers of different sexes. Throughout the interviews, representatives of leading publishers and journal editors argued that OPR was limited in its ability to address the gender equality issues as it does not by default change how reviewers are selected or determine whether the balance is achieved among the reviewers and editorial boards.

The lack of diversity on editorial boards generates disparities in editorial and peer reviews, which also contributes to gender disparities in scholarly communication. Many interviewees argued that governing boards have to be more diverse to be able to collectively overcome issues related to biases. Additionally, the lack of data proving such disparities and their effects does not allow to make data driven decisions. For example, interviewees reported that Elsevier recently introduced a new field of research on gender balance for journal editorial boards and began to not only mandate data collection on gender representation on the editorial boards, but also to retroactively collect data in this area. They sought to have the data that would allow to analyse the researcher environment more broadly, and enable discussions about what actions have to be taken to address issues affecting this environment. In such a way, they were able to identify not only the number of women relative to men on editorial boards, but also the problems such as common usage of language, which is geared towards masculinity, that affect scholarly communication.

⁶¹ <https://implicit.harvard.edu/implicit/takeatest.html> (choose Social attitudes, where there are IATs on, for example, gender and science, gender and career, age, disability, race)

⁶² https://www.nature.com/articles/nn0399_197

4.4.3. Gender diversity in review panels

There is a highly successful initiative in Germany to monitor gender diversity and integrating gender equality into its most prominent funding programme, called Excellence Initiative.⁶³ This initiative was founded in 2005 to strengthen Germany's research landscape. Selectively allocated public funding is awarded to the "Universities of Excellence" if they qualify by establishing and committing to the three lines of funding, including Graduate Schools, Clusters of Excellence and Institutional Strategies. Competitive funding allows such elite universities to conduct cutting-edge research and raise their profile internationally. The German Research Foundation (DFG), which is one of the administrators of the initiative, established gender equality as a selection criterion for grants in its Research-Oriented Standards on Gender Equality, and in such a way embedded gender equality in research excellence.⁶⁴ Along with that, they offer financial incentives for designing equality measures as part of the institutional grant proposal. By 2014, the DFG also started demanding that research proposals would specify the number of women included in the project along with a statistical report on gender equality from each university. Although such requirements are often perceived as 'political' in this context, respondents reported that compliance with this standard has eventually become one of the signs of quality for work in the German research environment. Competition among PIs and universities for funding encouraged attention to this criterion. However, there are no plans to address equality in the evaluation of research or composition of review panels.

Another successful initiative is implemented by Swedish Research Council. They monitor the peer review process for grant applications to ensure that a diverse group of researchers make up the review panels, including people who are open to new approaches, cross-disciplinarity and the margins of the research fields or topics that are usually understudied by other researchers.⁶⁵ More detailed introductions, case-based workshops and training in gender equality have been organised for various review panels on implicit biases. Many interview respondents regarded this practice as an exemplary model for recognising the value of collaboration, cross-disciplinarity, and the effort to conduct research in the margins of various fields. These efforts also advance the recognition and evaluation procedures of female applicants.

4.4.4. Gender bias in research dissemination

Gender imbalance across many fields science knowledge production (what questions are asked, how analysis is conducted), application (what discoveries are selected for innovation, who is involved in idea creation) and communication (who is perceived as the target audience) across all the mediums. Therefore, it is necessary to apply gender analysis to every step of the research process from designing a search strategy for the literature to identify background, to collection and analysis of data, to drawing conclusions and identifying shortcomings, and communicating results.

Interview respondents reported that not all areas of research have sex/gender aspects relevant to the content of the study itself (e.g. gravitational waves), but they might be relevant for outreach (e.g. encouraging girls and boys in schools to take up physics) and public engagement activities, for researcher training (on historical gender bias in science knowledge and methods), and for policy recommendations (e.g. feeding the pipeline, maximising impact of investment in research).

⁶³ <https://www.exzellenz.tum.de/en/what-is-the-excellence-initiative/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.ssc.wisc.edu/~mferree/wp/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/zippel-ferree-zimmermann-2016.pdf>

⁶⁵ <https://publikationer.vr.se/en/product/a-gender-neutral-process-gender-equality-observations-in-the-swedish-research-councils-review-panels-2016/>

OpenUP identified four relevant gender aspects that we have analysed in context of our innovative dissemination case studies.⁶⁶ The first aspect relates to the gender distribution within the team responsible for research and dissemination. The second aspect pertains to the representation of gender, gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the disseminated materials. The third aspect regards gender sensitivity and inclusiveness of the used dissemination tools, platforms and strategies. Finally, the fourth gender aspect relates to the target audience, e.g. their gender distribution, and any relevant gender-sensitive aspects in their regard (e.g. when disseminating research results from medicine). Members of the scientific societies and journal editors among the interviewees supported identification of such aspects when disseminating research. Other respondents, particularly researchers, however, insisted that gender-regulating measures in dissemination would not be able to achieve gender equity, but on the contrary, add additional requirements and workload to researchers, preventing them from conducting research.

In addition, the interviewed journal editors and policymakers recognised that they have to advance the quality and transparency of research by promoting sex- and gender-specific examination of publications and data. The European Association of Science Editors (EASE) established a Gender Policy Committee in 2012 and developed a set of guidelines for the reporting of Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER).⁶⁷ A panel of 13 experts (eight females, five males) representing nine countries, created a comprehensive procedure for reporting of sex and gender information in study design, data analyses, results and interpretation of findings. They are also aimed at editors to use as a practical instrument to evaluate a research manuscript and as a vehicle to raise awareness among authors and reviewers. They also emphasise careful use of the terms sex and gender.

4.4.5. Gender bias in research evaluation

Innovative dissemination tools also have the potential to help women to gain better recognition of their expertise and assist them in putting that expertise forward into the community. The OpenUP survey found that female researchers are more likely to disseminate their research through non-traditional dissemination methods and to engage the public (press releases, popular science publications and events for general public) compared to male researchers.⁶⁸ These efforts, however, are not acknowledged by traditional evaluation methods and research impact measurements. Many respondents especially stakeholders from research/academia and publishers insisted that it is therefore essential not only to equip each female researcher with adequate information and tools to promote their research and expertise but also to introduce ways to recognise and measure their efforts to use innovative tools. These actions may improve the recognition of female researchers, as it would take dissemination through non-traditional dissemination channels into account.

Altmetrics could potentially improve the recognition and evaluation of female researchers because it offers the possibility to implement a more comprehensive evaluation of individuals. Throughout the interviews, it was often noted that women are vastly underrepresented among the most productive researchers. In some cases, this may be due to the fact that women tend to engage in more interdisciplinary research.

Interviewed service providers and researchers argued that if article-level metrics were combined with author level metrics instead of using the Impact Factor, a more diverse set of measures and greater levels of transparency would allow to more accurately depict each researcher's levels of productivity. While, article-level metrics refer to a measure of impact that draws from a variety of different data sources,

⁶⁶ See Kraker, P. et al. (2017).

⁶⁷ <https://researchintegrityjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s41073-016-0007-6#Tab1>

⁶⁸ See Kraker, P. et al. (2017).

including traditional (e.g. times cited) and new (e.g. tweets),⁶⁹ author level metrics are defined as an attempt to quantify impact by analysing citations of an individual author's publications.⁷⁰ Thus, interviewees called for a more extensive use of the combination of these metrics as they have different but complementary abilities to capture impact of each individual researcher much more accurately, including females.

There are efforts to respond to this call already. For instance, PlumX categorises research metrics into five categories,⁷¹ helping to explain the use of data by citations, usage, mentions, captures, and social media. This has the potential to positively alter the process of evaluation of individual researchers, because it helps to show what has a bigger impact in different areas, e.g. driving policy or academic research by assessing usage, downloads, captures when bookmarking, favouring, research mentions in blog posts or Wikipedia links, likes and tweets, in addition to just measuring citations.

4.4.6. Conclusions and further steps: Open Science and RRI to advance gender equality in research

Despite some progress in the past decade, gender inequity in research and academia is still evident. National initiatives at country levels aim to raise awareness on the issue and promote practices that could increase gender equity. In addition, various initiatives are introduced by research organisations, funders and publishers that aim to decrease the gender bias in *reviews-assess-disseminate* cycle of scholarly publishing. Aspects of OS or RRI also offer some solutions by introducing transparency and inclusiveness to this cycle. However, they also pose risks and many researchers and other stakeholders still question their unconditional applicability and implementation.

In the next phase of the project, the research team will conduct further research in this area. Partners from all thematic work packages will collaborate to elaborate key issues as well as good practices related to gender in peer review, dissemination and altmetrics. The main conclusions will be presented and validated in a workshop involving key stakeholders and experts from research organisations, funders, libraries, research councils and policy makers. The final synthesis and policy report will be produced, highlighting gender-specific good practices and policy recommendations for peer review, impact measurement and research dissemination.

5. Policies in the areas of open peer review, innovative dissemination and altmetrics in eight selected countries in Europe

The section below provides an in-depth overview of OS policies and initiatives in eight European countries. Initial data was collected via desk research and validated with OpenUP consortium partners residing in respective countries. At a later stage the information coming from the interviews was also added to this overview.

⁶⁹ <https://sparcopen.org/our-work/article-level-metrics/>

⁷⁰ <http://libguides.einstein.yu.edu/c.php?g=123507&p=808389>

⁷¹ <https://plumanalytics.com/learn/about-metrics/>

Austria

There is a strong movement for OS in Austria, in particular with regards to OA to publications.⁷² Austria is one of the very first countries to develop a National Open Innovation Strategy, a comprehensive policy framework aimed at promoting collaboration between industry, science, public administration and society, thus increasing Austria's innovative strength and competitiveness by means of open innovations.⁷³ Adopted in 2016, it aims to cover three action areas and apply 14 concrete policy measures. As a result, Austria has developed a unique approach to tackling various OS issues. Many institutions have OA policies in place, including several universities and research institutions, such as the University of Vienna.⁷⁴ Institutions and organisations that are most active in promoting Open Science in Austria include the Open Access Network Austria (OANA), the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), Universities Austria (UNIKO), the Austrian Chapter of Open Knowledge (OK-AT), the Austrian Library Consortium Cooperation E-Media Austria (KEMÖ), the Austrian Academy of Sciences (OAW), and the Austrian Library Network Ltd (OBVSG). For example, the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), Austria's central organisation for funding science and basic research, requires and supports **Open Access** for peer-reviewed publications that publish results funded via FWF grants.⁷⁵

Many different stakeholders are working together to support the transition to OA. Large funding institutions such as the FWF support the OA transition by trying to flip journals to pick the **gold** route (funders do not support hybrid OA). Libraries, ministries and university administrations have a growing interest in the topic as well. Therefore, they try to promote OA policies and open up different areas to innovation, for instance by bringing open citizen science, OS and open education closer together. Working Groups were established to define overlapping issues across all of these topics. Various projects (e.g. e-Infrastructures Austria, see below) are receiving government funding to establish e-infrastructures to provide that technical support needed in the system. As a result, templates of RDM plans were developed and provided to scientific communities.

UNIKO together with FWF established the Open Access Network Austria (OANA) at the end of 2012, to 1) coordinate OA recommendations by Austrian research organisations, research funding agencies, and research policy; 2) formulate uniform positions in relation to information providers; and 3) serve as a contact point and information resource for researchers, research organisations, and research policy.⁷⁶ In 2015, OANA produced a set of recommendations for the implementation of OA policy, the main recommendation is a proposal to mandate all scholarly publication activities in Austria to be OA by 2025.⁷⁷ The OANA recommendations also call for all research organisations to have publicly accessible and internationally registered repositories by 2018 for the long term archiving of publications. According to the OANA, 20 institutions in Austria have adopted an OA policy and signed the Berlin Declaration. EU Network PASTEUR4OA determined that the FWF has one of the most effective public funder OA policies in the world.

The Austrian Library Consortium Cooperation E-Media Austria (KEMÖ) established a permanent working group that investigates and monitors publication costs, and the sharing of burdens between institutions in

⁷² ERA Portal Austria (2015). Policy Brief. Open Science, pp. 9-10 <https://era.gv.at/object/document/2279>

⁷³ http://openinnovation.gv.at/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/OI_Barrierefrei_Englisch.pdf

⁷⁴ K. Buschmann et al. (2015), Open Science in Österreich: Ansätze und Status. In IWP, 66/2–3, 2015, 137–145

⁷⁵ <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/>

⁷⁶ K. Buschmann, K. Rieck, K. (2015), Bericht zur 2. Informationsveranstaltung des Open Access Network Austria (OANA). <http://www.oana.at/veranstaltungen/veranstaltung-21012015/>

⁷⁷ Bauer, B., Blechl, G., Bock, C., Danowski, P., Ferus, A., Graschopf, A., et al. (2015, November 30). Recommendations for the Transition to Open Access in Austria. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.34079>

Austria. Additionally, it centrally negotiates license agreement with information providers (e.g. publishers). In collaboration with FWF, KEMÖ negotiated one of the first almost cost-neutral OA deals with publishers (hybrid OA payments are offset against subscriptions and OA publishing is part of this big deal). Currently, it aims to further reorganise publishing contracts to ensure that research publications are automatically published OA.

Regarding **opening the research data**, FWF requires data produced with their funding to be available for free whenever legally and ethically possible.⁷⁸ The recommendations from OANA state that as a transitional measure to Open Science, research organisations and legislators in Austria should adopt the principles of The Hague Declaration on Knowledge Discovery in the Digital Age and ensure that data can be searchable and reusable for scholarly purposes. With support from the Nationalstiftung für Forschung, Technologie und Entwicklung, FWF has initiated the pilot programme Open Research Data (ORD) in order to create models for the openness of research data.

An important initiative in Austria was the national e-Infrastructures Austria project funded by the Ministry of Science, Research and Economics, which ran from 2014 to 2017.⁷⁹ The objective of this project was to establish and develop Repository Infrastructures for digital resources in research and science, including open sharing of research data, throughout Austria. Among other outputs, the project created a model policy for research data management in research institutions based on an “open-by-default” approach.⁸⁰ This project had two follow-up projects, which both started in 2017. The Austrian Transition to Open Access (AT2OA) project aims to contribute to the transformation from closed to open access to scholarly publications by initiating supporting measures (such as an analysis of potential impacts of an OA transition, the funding of OA business models, the establishment of OA publication funds and the promotion of OA publications and alternative OA publication models).⁸¹ The project seeks to increase the OA publication output of Austrian scholars.⁸² These measures are implemented alongside networking activities and knowledge transfer measures. The focus of the e-Infrastructures Austria Plus project is on developing services for data management at Austrian universities. Both projects are funded by the Ministry of Science, Research and Economics and will run from 2017 to 2020.

Some interviewees stated that ORD is not a large component of the scientific discourse in Austria yet, as there are still many fears among researchers about sharing data. Despite the efforts to experiment on a community level with ORD, respondents reported that lack of funding is one of the biggest reasons for the absence of new projects that would build flexible infrastructures suitable for ORD. Additionally, the lack of incentives and rewards add to researchers’ fears about sharing data openly.

Discussions surrounding the adoption of **open peer review** are taking place within OANA, however no formal action has been taken regarding OPR in Austria.

In terms of **innovative dissemination**, it was incorporated into ‘Strategy 2020’, a document that contains proposals and recommendations for the development of the Austrian innovation system in the future, released by the Austrian Council for Research and Technology Development in 2009.⁸³ The Austrian Open Innovation Strategy addressed new forms of dissemination including measures for building up

⁷⁸ <http://www.fwf.ac.at/en/research-funding/open-access-policy/>

⁷⁹ <http://e-infrastructures.at/en/the-project/>

⁸⁰ e-Infrastructures Austria (2016). Model Policy for research data management (RDM) at Austrian research institutions. Phaidra. <http://phaidra.univie.ac.at/o:459162>

⁸¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/austria-opens-science-new-projects-in-2017>

⁸² University of Vienna (2017), Auftakt zur "Austrian Transition to Open Access" (AT2OA). News item from 21st March 2017: <https://openaccess.univie.ac.at/news-events/detailansicht/news/auftakt-zum-projekt-at2oa/>

⁸³ http://www.rat-fte.at/strategy-documents/articles/stategy_documents.html

competences, and creating new open science and open innovation methods for the collaboration between external partners and stakeholders in an interdisciplinary context. Additionally, the OANA working group on Open Access and Scholarly Communication seeks to influence scholarly communication through the Vienna Principles, a document for scholarly communication.⁸⁴ They represent a coherent frame of reference for the debate on how to improve the current system. The 12 principles illustrate a vision for science communication in the 21st century. The application of the principles has been promoted across all the OA, OS communities and initiatives, but is not a common standard yet. The working group is now drafting Version 2.0 of the Vienna Principles, which should encourage further and better uptake of innovative communication strategies.

Innovation and research centres in Austria sponsor events aimed at raising awareness among researchers about innovative dissemination. Individual initiatives to disseminate using innovative ways are emerging. For instance, Digital Humanities (DH) is an open network of institutional partners in Austria joining efforts to realize a new understanding of humanities research in a digital environment.⁸⁵

There are no specific policies or practices in Austria in the area of **altmetrics**. In the OANA recommendations on the transition to Open Access in Austria, altmetrics is put forth as one of the transitional measures on the path to more Open Science practices in the country. Recently, more individual attempts to take up altmetrics have emerged. For instance, the University of Vienna is testing a new system: scores for publications internally. At the University Library of Vienna, there is also a department working on altmetrics to support rectors and researchers.⁸⁶ They organise regular international summer schools on altmetrics. However, many interview respondents reported that for many researchers it is still unclear what altmetrics stand for. As a result, trust in their validity is limited.

Table 5. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, ID and altmetrics in Austria.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified in innovative dissemination.	No policies/practices identified.
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
No policies/practices identified	In 2009, the Austrian Council for Research and Technology Development released ‘Strategy 2020’, a document that contains proposals and recommendations for the future development of the Austrian innovation system. Additionally, the Austrian Open Innovation Strategy more recently addressed new forms of dissemination along with measures for building up competences and open science and open innovation methods for collaborating with external partners and stakeholders in an interdisciplinary context. Other initiatives are coming from within the scientific community and other stakeholders in defining how research communication should be improved.	Altmetrics are used and presented by various universities, libraries or repositories. For instance, the University of Vienna is testing a new system: scores for publications internally. Also, the recommendations of OANA on the transition to Open Access in Austria recommend using alternative evaluation systems (altmetrics) when evaluating researchers and their work.

⁸⁴ <http://viennaprinciples.org/>

⁸⁵ <http://digital-humanities.at/en>

⁸⁶ <http://bibliothek.univie.ac.at/bibliometrie/>

Germany

The most prominent Open Science statement stemming from Germany is the “Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities”. By May 2017, 587⁸⁷ international research institutions signed the declaration; more than 30 of which are German organisations including the German Rectors’ Conference, the Max Planck Society, Leibniz Association etc.⁸⁸ Stressing the importance of the document, the **Open Access** debate in Germany is largely defined by the Berlin Declaration.⁸⁹ The goal of the declaration is to promote and support the transition to the electronic OA paradigm.⁹⁰ In Germany both forms of Open Access, i.e. **green** and **gold** routes are promoted and encouraged.

There is a diverse landscape of OA as a result of the federal system in Germany. A Federal Agenda Strategy set by the federal Ministries of Education and Research is committed to developing comprehensive OA strategies at the federal level which are implemented through the universities that belong to the federal state (e.g. Schleswig-Holstein, Berlin, Baden-Württemberg).⁹¹ Germany has set up national coordination bodies and networks to work on OA strategies and policies. Other institutes and organisations complement these with their own OA initiatives. The Max Planck Society has developed a roadmap for a large-scale transition to OA by 2020.⁹² The Alliance of German Science Organisations and the German Initiative for Network Information (DINI) has formulated common positions concerning OA topics. The major research funder Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG) and the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) have clear commitment towards OA and have incorporated certain OA publishing requirements into their funded research.⁹³

A growing number of German universities adopted OA policies. According to the interviewees, this happened in response to the requirements set out by funders such as DFG. They also reported that there is a high coverage of OA across institutions at all levels in Germany. As a result, all the major research organisations in the country are committed to OA2020, a global alliance seeking to accelerate the transition to OA.⁹⁴ The OA2020 Initiative was established at the 12th Berlin Open Access conference in 2015, which gathered thought leaders in the global Open Access movement. Building on the 2003 Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities, and the Mission Statement of 2015, OA2020 is founded on analysis that demonstrates that there is already enough money within journal publishing to allow for a cost-neutral transition to OA.⁹⁵

Interviews conducted with the German experts revealed that many of the major German stakeholders are also currently involved in a collaborative initiative advancing Open Science. The DEAL project, which is headed by German Rector’s Conference, has decided to take action in promoting OA by negotiating a nationwide licencing agreement with Elsevier journal portfolio (negotiations are still on-going).⁹⁶ Action

⁸⁷ <https://openaccess.mpg.de/319790/Signatories>

⁸⁸ <https://oa2020.org/about/>

⁸⁹ Open Access. Opportunities and Challenges - a Handbook. European Commission / German Commission for UNESCO, 2008. http://www.unesco.de/fileadmin/medien/Dokumente/Kommunikation/Handbook_Open_Access_English.pdf

⁹⁰ <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>

⁹¹ Not all feral states have such statements in place, and there is no umbrella strategy.

⁹² The initiative can be accessed at <https://oa2020.org/> ; more about the initiative: <https://www.mpg.de/openaccess/oa2020>

⁹³ <https://www.openaire.eu/oa-germany>

⁹⁴ <https://oa2020.org/mission/>

⁹⁵ Schimmer, R., Geschuhn, K. K., & Vogler, A. (2015). Disrupting the subscription journals’ business model for the necessary large-scale transformation to open access. doi:10.17617/1.3.

⁹⁶ <https://www.sub.uni-goettingen.de/en/news/details/voraussichtlich-keine-volltexte-von-zeitschriften-des-elsevier-verlags-ab-dem-112017/>

was taken in response to Elsevier’s refusal to step into a new type of contract, which secures that all publications with corresponding authors from Germany are made openly available. To strengthen the bargaining power of German research institutions, more than 60 German institutions cancelled their Elsevier journal subscriptions. By introducing such measures German universities hope to push journals to comply with the principles of OA and change the principles of institutional agreements with publishers (from subscriptions to agreements which cover the costs of OA publishing).

In terms of **open access to research data**, there are several initiatives in Germany. The Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data.org) was developed with co-funding from the German Research Foundation and is operated under the umbrella of the DataCite foundation. In 2010, the Alliance of German Science Organisations (including organisations like Alexander von Humboldt Foundation, Helmholtz Association, German Rectors’ Conference, Leibniz Association and Max Planck Society) adopted the Principles for the Handling of Research Data⁹⁷ and also created a working group on research data. It is a part of its priority initiative called Digital Information, which was extended to run for a second phase from 2013 until 2017⁹⁸. Moreover, since 2014 the joint nestor/DINI working group on research data has been developing guidance and training material as well as organising events on research data management.⁹⁹

No policies relating to **OPR** or **innovative dissemination** were identified at national or organisational levels. According to interviewees, OPR is being discussed only at a low level by a minority of researchers. However, due to a fairly traditional culture in German scientific communities these voices are not being heard. There are individual initiatives such as the interactive open access journal *“Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics”* that have been successfully providing OPR since 2001. This journal has an innovative two-stage publication process involving the scientific discussion forum called Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions (ACPD), which has been designed to foster scientific discussion, maximise the effectiveness and transparency of scientific quality assurance, enable rapid publication of new scientific results and make scientific publications freely accessible.¹⁰⁰

Finally, no policies relating to **altmetrics** in Germany were identified. Nevertheless, there are practices already aimed at incorporating these new metrics into the scientific discourse. For example, the German Research Foundation is currently funding the metrics project, which aims at gaining a deeper understanding of altmetrics as well as evaluating altmetrics and their technical foundations.¹⁰¹

Table 6. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, ID and altmetrics in Germany.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified	DFG funded project: *metrics. The project aims at assessing and analysing altmetrics and its perceptions among researchers and other stakeholders. ¹⁰² A project studies Open

⁹⁷ <http://www.allianzinitiative.de/en/core-activities/research-data/principles/>

⁹⁸ <http://www.allianzinitiative.de/en/core-activities/research-data/>

⁹⁹ http://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/AG_Forschungsdaten

¹⁰⁰ https://www.atmospheric-chemistry-and-physics.net/about/aims_and_scope.html

¹⁰¹ <https://www.sub.uni-goettingen.de/en/news/details/start-of-new-project-funded-by-the-german-research-foundation-dfg-metrics/>

¹⁰² <https://www.sub.uni-goettingen.de/en/news/details/start-of-new-project-funded-by-the-german-research-foundation-dfg-metrics/>

		Access usage statistics and whether such statistics could be an alternative to the journal impact factor which is currently widely used as an important evaluation method. ¹⁰³ Some relevant research activities, e.g. at GESIS, Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (HIIG), DZHW.
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Greece

In Greece, the **Open Access** movement is in the developing stage. A draft legislation in the areas of research and technology mentions an obligation to provide OA to all publicly funded research via the **green** route. However, the budget for the implementation of this particular article has not been made public yet.¹⁰⁴ According to the interviewed stakeholders there is a growing understanding of OA and ORD in Greece. This was attributed to the role that librarians play in raising awareness through various events such as the OA week or training seminars on the topics like open linked data.¹⁰⁵ OpenAIRE has contributed to arranging these events with the National Documentation Centre (EKT).¹⁰⁶

As of 2016, only two universities (the Technical University of Crete and the International Hellenic University) adopted an OA policy, following support provided by the EKT.¹⁰⁷ OA is further promoted through the EKT’s ePublishing platform.¹⁰⁸ University and research libraries formed the Hellenic Academic Libraries Link (HEAL-Link)¹⁰⁹ to discuss OA topics and formulate declarations, strategies and policies on commonly agreed principles. In addition, HEAL-link, which is comprised of 38 HEIs, 14 technological education institutes, 8 other libraries, the Academy of Athens and the National Library of Greece, has developed a platform that hosts more than 11,000 full-text electronic journals. In Greece, structural funds are used to fund most of the Open Science initiatives. However, national public research funders have not adopted OA policies yet.

There is no policy or mandate relating to research data management in the country. According to the respondents, only the projects that are funded by Horizon2020 take into account RDM in the interest of complying with the funder’s requirements. Nonetheless, some institutions are starting to explore this area as well. For example, the Technical University of Crete dedicated a paragraph of their institutional OA policy to explain and encourage ORD.¹¹⁰

At national and organisational levels, we did not identify any policies or initiatives relating to **OPR, innovative dissemination** and **altmetrics**.

Table 7. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, ID and altmetrics in Greece.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified.	No policies/practices identified

¹⁰³ <http://www.dini.de/projekte/oa-statistik/english/>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.innovationpolicyplatform.org/content/greece-open-science-country-note>

¹⁰⁵

<http://palc23.lib.auth.gr/%CE%BD%CE%AD%CE%B1/%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%BC%CE%B9%CE%BD%CE%AC%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BF>

¹⁰⁶ <http://www.openaccess.gr/el/oa-events>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/oa-greece>

¹⁰⁸ <http://epublishing.ekt.gr/>

¹⁰⁹ <http://www.heal-link.gr/?lang=en>

¹¹⁰ https://www.tuc.gr/fileadmin/users_data/library/_uploads/open_access_policy_on_TUC-Library_teliko.pdf

Italy

The Italian **Open Access** movement was built by librarians, researchers and IT professionals through bottom-up approach. The first official action that endorsed the Berlin Declaration was the Messina Declaration¹¹¹ (2004), which is currently signed by 71 university and 15 research organisations, such as CNR (National Research Council), ISS (National Institute of Health in Italy), INFN (National Institute of Nuclear Physics). The PLEIADI¹¹² (Portal for Italian Electronic Scholarly Literature in Institutional Archives) was launched by the University consortia - CASPUR and CILEA, now CINECA in the Messina conference.¹¹³ At the beginning, this platform provided direct access to institutional repositories as well as to information on OA events and scientific literature. Since 2008, the Italian Wiki on Open Access is another source of information on OA.¹¹⁴

In 2006, the Conference of Italian Universities Rectors (CRUI) established a working group on OA to support the implementation of OA initiatives. This group developed a series of guidelines and recommendations for the creation on institutional repositories, OA journals, metadata preservation, that have been adopted by several universities. In 2013, Article 4 of Law 112 was introduced, which requires that all research outputs resulting from publicly funded projects, including data, has to be made available OA either by adopting the **green** or **gold** road. This applies when public funds make up 50% or more of the research budget.¹¹⁵

Other actions and initiatives to implement OA policies are taking place. The Registry of Open Access Repository Mandates and Policies (ROARMAP) contains Open Access mandates provided by 24 universities and research organizations in Italy.¹¹⁶ There are some universities that mention an OA mandate in their statutes, others are in the process of approving them.¹¹⁷ The Agency for Digital Italy (AgID) and the Italian CNR initiated the Science and Technology Digital Library that aims at providing public access to scientific data and information free of charge.¹¹⁸ At the request of the government, a network of Institutional Points of Reference in each research organisation and university has been established to discuss OA topics and formulate commonly agreed declarations, strategies and policies. Some private research funders also require publishing OA (e.g. Telethon and Fondazione Cariplo).

Interviews with national experts from Italy revealed that librarians and researchers are currently debating **ORD**. However no specific national? policy has been adopted for research data yet. In 2014, the Ministry of Education, University and Research launched a pilot programme called SIR (Scientific Independence of Young Researchers), which mandates OA to all publications, including the corresponding data. Specific instructions on meta-data are also included. Some universities have also been developing a policy model

¹¹¹ <http://eprints-phd.biblio.unitn.it/help/MessinaEN.pdf>

¹¹² <http://find.openarchives.it/>

¹¹³ Caspur, Cilea and Cineca were three publicly funded consortia that offered innovative and technologically advanced services to Italian Universities, the Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR) and research organizations. In 2012 Caspur and Cilea were merged into Cineca. Cineca is a non-profit Consortium, made up of 70 Italian universities, 8 Italian Research Institutions and the Italian Ministry of Education. It develops advanced Information Technology applications and services, acting like a trait-d'union between the academic world, the sphere of pure research and the world of industry and Public Administration: <https://www.cineca.it/en/content/about-us>

¹¹⁴ http://wiki.openarchives.it/index.php/Pagina_principale

¹¹⁵ <https://www.researchitaly.it/en/news/towards-an-open-access-italian-network/>

¹¹⁶ http://roarmap.eprints.org/cgi/search/archive/advanced?screen=Search&dataset=archive&action_search=Search&country=380&policy_maker_name_merge=ALL&policy_maker_name=&policy_adoption=&policy_effective=&mandate_content_types_merge=ANY&apc_fun_url_merge=ALL&apc_fun_url=&satisfyall=ALL&order=policy_maker_name

¹¹⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/oa-italy>

¹¹⁸ <http://stdl.cnr.it/en/>

concerning data management and diffusion.¹¹⁹ There is a working group, which released an ORD policy model.¹²⁰ According to the interviewees, around 20-25 universities have already endorsed it. However, due to the lack of funding and other incentives, there is no strong commitment to institutional goals among researchers at universities.

At institutional level, we did not identify any policies relating to **OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics**. There are early experiments with OPR, arranged by the Association for the Promotion of Open Science (*AISA- Associazione Italiana per la promozione della Scienza Aperta*)¹²¹.

In terms of innovative dissemination and altmetrics, no national policies were adopted in Italy. Institutional repositories use Institutional Research Information System, IRIS software¹²², which is the new CRIS solution developed by Cineca for research assessment. Libraries and research offices are using PlumX quite extensively, according to the interview respondents. However, the Italian Agency for Research Assessment (ANVUR) has not adopted alternative metrics, which contributes to the fact that there are still low levels of awareness of altmetrics among the researchers in Italy.

Table 8. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, ID and altmetrics in Italy.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices identified.	No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
No policies/practices identified.	No policies/practices identified.	No policies/practices identified

Lithuania

Lithuania is one of few countries that has outlined obligations to disseminate research results in a legislation. Article 51 of Law No. XII-2534 on Higher Education and Research of the Republic of Lithuania¹²³, which was adopted in 2016, mandates the results of research funded by the state to be made available for the public, unless they have to be protected as intellectual property, commercial or state and official secrets. However, there is no mechanism designed to monitor the implementation of this provision. Hence, universities and other research organisations have to develop their own policies, procedures, guidance and monitoring systems for full implementation of OA to research results.

At the end of 2013, Research Council of Lithuania (RCL) became a coordinating body for the implementation of OA in Lithuania. The RCL adopted Guidelines on **Open Access** to Scientific Publications and Data in 2016. They are fully aligned with the Horizon 2020 OA mandate and Open Research Data Pilot, and the European Commission recommendation released in 2012 on access to and preservation of scientific information. In the guidelines, the **green** route of OA is favoured. A transitional period for the implementation of the Guidelines will last until 31 December 2020. If non-compliance is detected during this period, warning measures apply and in some cases, funding for the projects may be suspended.¹²⁴ The large majority of public universities in Lithuania have also adopted guidelines on open access to publications. Having a considerable degree of institutional autonomy due to state funding, higher education institutions are able to define their own approach to open access to publications. However, all

¹¹⁹ http://wikimedia.sp.unipi.it/images/RDMpolicyresearchdata27_03_2017.pdf

¹²⁰ http://wikimedia.sp.unipi.it/images/RDMpolicyresearchdata27_03_2017.pdf

¹²¹ <http://aisa.sp.unipi.it/about-aisa/>

¹²² <https://www.cineca.it/en/content/iris-institutional-research-information-system>

¹²³ <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/en/legalAct/1a9058e049b311e6b5d09300a16a686c> (available in Lithuanian)

¹²⁴ <https://biblioteka.vu.lt/en/news/scholarly-communication/research-council-lithuania-adopted-its-guidelines-open-access>

the adopted guidelines for publications are closely aligned with the principles set out by the National Research Council.

Regarding **research data management**, the guidelines state that data associated with publications should be made available openly at the same time as the publication, and stored in an institutional or other suitable repository for not less than five years. Researchers are requested to develop data management plans, and the costs associated with data management can be covered by the RCL funding. Like in H2020, it is possible to opt out from opening the research data due to data protection, IPR and other reasons. In addition to the national guidelines on OA to Scientific Publications and Data, some Lithuanian research institutions have also adopted their guidelines on data management (e.g. Vilnius University, Kaunas Technology University).¹²⁵

In recent years there has been progress in Lithuania on developing infrastructures for preservation of scientific information. The Lithuanian Academic e-Library (eLABa), is a national aggregated OA repository started at the end of 2006. eLABa is in charge of developing the environment and tools, which allows preparation, collection, long-term preservation, and access to research and study e-documents created in Lithuania. The project National Open Access Research Data Archive MIDAS funded by EU Structural Funds was launched in 2012. MIDAS¹²⁶ includes 13 higher education institutions (HEIs) and research and medical institutions. The platform enables collection, processing, storing and analysing scientific research data and other relevant information in all fields of knowledge. It is free to access for any user without infringing copyright and intellectual property rights. Lithuanian research institutions recommend depositing research data on these platforms if funders have not foreseen other requirements.¹²⁷ Although research data depositing is generally at nascent stages, researchers in the fields of Physics, Mathematics and Computer Science extensively use the arXiv to deposit e-prints and scientific papers within these disciplines. The Predicted Crystallography Open Database (PCOD) is the most widely used repository in the area of life sciences in Lithuania.

In the Lithuanian scientific community, there are discussions taking place on **peer review**, determinants of its quality and recent developments of the processes.¹²⁸ However, no national or institutional initiatives currently exist to promote the uptake of open peer review practice.

Innovative dissemination of research is considered along with the overall science communication and promotion strategies in Lithuania. In 2005, the Lithuanian Ministry for Education and Science (MES) adopted a Strategy for Science and Technology promotion in Lithuania.¹²⁹ It stated that science communication towards the society should be more effective and separated target groups as well as the means available for communication. In addition, in 2007 the MES commissioned a study that identified the needs of science promotion in Lithuania and the main actions that could be implemented.¹³⁰ The study found that the largest share of activities to promote science are conducted by non-governmental organisations, and not by researchers themselves. The study also found that researchers lack incentives to engage in science promotion activities as these activities are not part of their evaluation process. One of the recommendations for the MES was to improve the skills for science communication and to support

¹²⁵ <https://biblioteka.vu.lt/naujienos/mokslines-komunikacija/vilniaus-universitetas-deklaravo-moksliniu-tyrimu-duomenu-valdymo>; <http://ktu.edu.lt/biblioteka/naujiena/patvirtinti-atvirosios-prieigos-prie-mokslo-publikaciju-ir-duomenu-nuostatai>

¹²⁶ <https://midas.lt/public-app.html#/apie-midas?lang=en>

¹²⁷ For example, the library of Vilnius University recommends using MIDAS for research data storage: <https://biblioteka.vu.lt/mokslui-ir-studijoms/mokslines-komunikacija/atviroji-prieiga>

¹²⁸ <http://serials.lt/discussion-peer-review-in-scientific-journal-measuring-the-quality/>

¹²⁹ <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/TAIS.255873>

¹³⁰ VšĮ Socialinių inovacijų institutas, 2007. Mokslo populiarinimo poreikio analizė. Studija.

science promotion activities among researchers. Interviewees indicated that researchers in the fields of Natural Sciences and Technology tend to engage more with these innovative dissemination methods than in any other fields.

Although these two documents outlined recommendations and approaches to be taken in science communication, only a few measures were implemented. The financial crisis of 2009 also redirected the financial resources of the government from implementing science communication activities to other policy areas.¹³¹ Currently, the science promotion is still mostly actively carried out by non-governmental institutions or individual initiatives due to the lack of a consistent government policy and coordination.

In 2011, Lithuanian Academy of Sciences (LAS) together with several other organisations started a project aiming at developing a System of National Science Popularisation.¹³² The project was funded by the European Social Fund and received a new grant in 2017 that will allow the project to continue until 2019. The initiative aims at ensuring effective and long-term coordination of science promotion activities in Lithuania. The current project encompasses a broad range of activities that promote science as well as more specific innovative dissemination activities such as TV programmes, science cafes, festivals, and many science-themed events for children and youth.

The impacts of outputs produced by Lithuanian researchers are evaluated through traditional indicators (such as the number of publications, their ranking and publishing in high ranking journals).¹³³ **Altmetrics** is not currently included in such evaluations. Still, various research institutions and libraries present and provide advice to researchers on altmetrics and how it can be used.¹³⁴

Table 9. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics in Lithuania.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices identified	National science promotion strategy was adopted in 2015 but not implemented to the full extent.	No policies/practices identified
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
No policies/practices identified	Some universities are involved in the project of development and implementation of a System of National Science Popularization funded by European Social Fund. The project partners work to develop an overall science promotion strategy that include innovative research dissemination tools.	No unified strategy for the use of altmetrics exist in Lithuania. However, Altmetrics is presented by various universities and libraries as possible indicators to be used by researchers. There are trainings and information provided to researchers on the possible use and value of altmetrics.

Switzerland

In January 2017, the Swiss National Strategy on **Open Access** was adopted with the ambition to make all the publicly funded research available free of charge by 2024.¹³⁵ The strategy aims at providing public

¹³¹ Maskoliūnas, R. 2014. Mokslo Populiarinimo sistema. Lietuvos Mokslų Akademija, Vilnius.

¹³² <http://mail.ma.lt/lt/es-sf-projektai/nacionalines-mokslo-populiarinimo-priemoniu-sistemos-sukurimas-ir-igyvendinimas-2007-2013>

¹³³ Mokslo in Studijų stebėsenos ir analizės centras, 2016. Lietuvos Mokslo ir studijų būklės apžvalga. Studijos, Mokslas, Inovacijos.

¹³⁴ For example, see Vilnius University Library webpage: <https://biblioteka.vu.lt/mokslui-ir-studijoms/mokslone-komunikacija/mokslometrija/alternatyvus-vertinimo-rodikliai>

¹³⁵ https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Hochschulpolitik/Open_Access/P06_7.01-01_Open_Access_strategy_EN.pdf

access to research publications via the Internet or via open databases as soon as possible. The State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) entrusted *swissuniversities* (Rectors' Conference of Swiss Higher Education Institutions) to prepare this strategy. To successfully implement it, *swissuniversities* are contributing by preparing a specific implementation plan.

Switzerland supports the principle of open electronic access to scientific knowledge nationally and internationally, through the SNSF (Swiss National Science Foundation). In addition, the largest research funder SNSF pursues both **green** and **gold** open access roads (direct costs of publishing are included in the project budget up to a ceiling of CHF 3000).¹³⁶ The SNSF requires grantees to provide OA to research results.¹³⁷ The foundation has prepared a monitoring report for self-evaluation. The report states that between October 2013 and August 2015 about 40% of SNSF-funded scientific publications in Switzerland were OA.¹³⁸ It is important to note that the SNSF guidelines are specific to open access, which means that it has no specific clauses on OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics.

In order to promote **open research data** practices in Switzerland, a funding programme P-2 “Scientific information: access, processing and safeguarding” was launched by the CRUS in 2014. The P-2 program funds the development of national solutions in the area of digital scientific information. It aims at building up a service network for the Swiss scientific community that would enable easy access to publications and data, and at the same time could provide tools for processing and safeguarding them. Two main documents outline the programme and its implementation. The first one is the National Strategy of the programme, which outlines the setup of the programme, funding conditions and the key focus areas.¹³⁹ The second document is the White Paper for a Swiss Information Provisioning and Processing Infrastructure 2020 that provides a more detailed technical information on the basic aspects of the programme.¹⁴⁰ It has documented the framework conditions and procedure for delivering the national strategy and, in particular, defined the measures for the implementation of the strategy during the funding period that lasted until 2016. The programme was renewed in 2017. The White Paper also has provided recommendations for action in the RDM area in Switzerland.

Through the P-2 programme, *swissuniversities* funded several projects that will address various themes in RDM, including data life-cycle management and set up of infrastructures for data and repository development.¹⁴¹ One of the funded projects has developed a beta version of a repository.¹⁴² The Open Research Data Platform Switzerland (ORD@CH) hosts a metadata catalogue of the data available at the institutions that are participating in the project.

The interviews with Swiss experts revealed that there is a growing awareness of OA, ORD and Open Science in Switzerland. Almost all universities in Switzerland already have an OA policy. For instance, librarians who in most cases support this policy in institutions are familiar with OA and ORD as well as the problems associated with them. Various Swiss-based international organisations such as CERN have adopted an OA policy as well.

¹³⁶ http://www.snf.ch/SiteCollectionDocuments/Dossiers/dos_OA_regelung_auf_einen_blick_e.pdf

¹³⁷ <http://www.snf.ch/en/theSNSF/research-policies/open-access/Pages/default.aspx>

¹³⁸ http://www.snf.ch/SiteCollectionDocuments/Monitoringbericht_Open_Access_2015_e.pdf

¹³⁹ https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Organisation/SUK-P/SUK_P-2/SUK_P-2_NationaleStrategie_20140403_EN.pdf

¹⁴⁰ https://www.swissuniversities.ch/fileadmin/swissuniversities/Dokumente/Organisation/SUK-P/SUK_P-2/WhitePaper_V1.1-EN.pdf

¹⁴¹ For example, <https://www.dlcm.ch/>, <http://linked.swissbib.ch/>.

¹⁴² <http://openresearchdata.ch/>

There are also various initiatives that facilitate the transition to OS. For example, the creation of a free online High Energy Physics (HEP) database called INSPIRE¹⁴³ (co-started with CERN), which includes bibliographic records and full-text preprints harvested from existing HEP databases such as arXiv, SPIRES and the CSS. There is also a project, initiated by CERN, called SCOAP3¹⁴⁴ aiming at paying publishers to organise peer review on an outsourced basis, allowing published research to be made freely available.

In the area of **OPR**, there are no national or organisational policies adopted in Switzerland. However, the SNSF aims at **supporting innovative research dissemination** via different avenues. For example, SNFS provides funding to projects that promote science and engagement through various activities.¹⁴⁵ The foundation also holds a competition on the best Scientific Image (including images and videos) in order to encourage researchers to present their work to the public and media.¹⁴⁶ Also, the foundation provides training to researchers on how to communicate with the media.¹⁴⁷

Additionally, *swissuniversities* has been initiating programs aimed at discovering **new directions for metrics** since 2008. Many stakeholders reported that the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)¹⁴⁸ published in 2013 has had a significant impact on expanding the understanding of how scientist’s contributions should be evaluated. This helped transforming the way hiring, promotion and funding decisions are made. However, interviews revealed that no formal policy on altmetrics is adopted, and a balance between quantitative as well as qualitative information is yet to be introduced.

Table 10. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics in Switzerland.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices identified	The SNSF is an institution mandated by the Federal Government to support basic science in all academic disciplines. SNSF aims to support innovative research dissemination via different avenues, including trainings for researchers on communication with media, providing funding to science communication projects and awarding best images or videos of science projects.	No policies/practices identified
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified

The Netherlands

In 2013 a national **Open Access policy** was adopted in the Netherlands. The Secretary of State for Education, Culture and Science outlined the position to the Dutch House of Representatives on OA.¹⁴⁹ The letter set an ambitious goal of switching scholarly publications in the Netherlands entirely to the **gold** route by 2024.¹⁵⁰ The Association of Universities in the Netherlands (VSNU) was entrusted to oversee this transition. With backing from the Dutch government, VSNU with support of some members of the Executive Board and library directors, recently negotiated several deals with major publishers (including

¹⁴³ <http://inspirehep.net/>

¹⁴⁴ <https://scoap3.org/>

¹⁴⁵ <http://www.snf.ch/en/funding/science-communication/agora/Pages/default.aspx>

¹⁴⁶ <http://www.snf.ch/en/funding/science-communication/image-competition/Pages/default.aspx>

¹⁴⁷ <http://www.snf.ch/en/funding/science-communication/media-courses/Pages/default.aspx>

¹⁴⁸ <http://dmm.biologists.org/content/dmm/early/2013/05/16/dmm.012955.full.pdf>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.government.nl/documents/parliamentary-documents/2014/01/21/open-access-to-publications>

¹⁵⁰ <http://www.openaccess.nl/en/in-the-netherlands/what-does-the-government-want>

Springer, Wiley and Elsevier) to make more Dutch scientific publications open in subscription journals with the aim of shifting the journals to an OA business model.¹⁵¹

Although these deals have been criticised as being very expensive and discouraging competition between journals, they showcase important policy-level efforts to move towards OA. Interviewees reported that among researchers this was perceived as a great success because they are now able to publish their research outputs without any costs in most cases. Information about the prepayment deals is available for authors on a national website.¹⁵² Still, some issues prevail, including the complexity of deals with publishers, which are not easy to adopt and to implement. According to the interviewees, some researchers do not know about the open access agreements with the publishers and do not select the option as they are afraid that they have to pay APCs at a later date.

The Advisory Council for Science, Technology and Innovation (AWTI)¹⁵³ advises the Dutch government and the Parliament on policy in the areas of scientific research, technological development and innovation. It is an independent Scientific Council consisting of 10 academics. In January 2016, the Council issued an advisory report¹⁵⁴ based on a Request for Advice from the State Secretary for Education, Culture and Science. The report describes Open Science, Open Access and Research Data Sharing and makes recommendations on how to progress in these areas nationally as well as at European level.

In terms of Open Science, in February 2017 Representatives from Dutch scientific and government organizations created the National Plan Open Science¹⁵⁵ to outline what national stakeholders have committed to achieve in the area of OS. The plan lists several goals and provides details of the parties intending to take action, as well as their timeframes. The main ambitions of the plan include ensuring OA to publications, optimal **re-use of research data**, educating support staff and new evaluation and reward systems. The funders also support opening of research data. The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO) has started a data management pilot in preparation for its future policy¹⁵⁶ and requires researchers to answer questions on data management when submitting research proposals. Also, the granted projects are requested to prepare data management plans. Although, interviewees reported that research data is not yet at the stage of being open, RDM is actively encouraged by libraries and universities. Many argued that a better infrastructure is needed to facilitate the transition to ORD.

Open Science in the Netherlands is supported by several bodies which have their own role. For example: the Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) provides the gateway to scholarly information in the Netherlands including data called NARCIS (<https://www.narcis.nl/>); and SURF has the ambition for to make the entire research process more accessible, and to simplify and facilitate collaboration and participation through policy and infrastructure. (<https://www.surf.nl/en/innovationprojects/open-science.html>)

At national and institutional levels, we did not identify any policies relating to **OPR**. In the area of **innovative dissemination**, AWTI have put forward recommendation for making the scientific publications understandable to general public. Some organisations and institutions promote various tools for research dissemination as well as provide guidance on how to use social media.¹⁵⁷ For example, the

¹⁵¹ Declan Butler, "Dutch Lead European Push to Flip Journals to Open Access."

¹⁵² <http://openaccess.nl>

¹⁵³ <https://english.awti.nl/>

¹⁵⁴ <https://www.awti.nl/documenten/adviezen/2016/01/20/vertaling-dare-to-share>

¹⁵⁵ <http://repository.tudelft.nl/islandora/object/uuid:9e9fa82e-06c1-4d0d-9e20-5620259a6c65?collection=research>

¹⁵⁶ <http://www.nwo.nl/en/policies/open+science/data+management>

¹⁵⁷ For example, University of Leiden <http://media.leidenuniv.nl/legacy/gedragcode-social-media-2012.pdf>

101 Innovations in Scholarly Communication was created by Utrecht University library staff.¹⁵⁸ Tools like ORCID are promoted along with others, although they are still not widely adopted by universities.

Regarding **altmetrics**, they are used to some extent by universities, libraries and other institutions. For example, since 2016 the UvA-DARE, the Digital Academic Repository in the Netherlands has been presenting altmetrics for articles in their repository.¹⁵⁹ In the Netherlands, the Standard Evaluation Protocol (SEP) describes the methods used to assess research conducted at Dutch universities. The SEP requests besides quantitative analysis (for example the number of articles) also a qualitative analysis (in the form of a narrative). Many universities engage in an alliance called Science in Transition to critically assess the current science system in the context of the 21st century needs.¹⁶⁰ KNAW, NWO, VSNU and others also seek to respond to the current needs by getting involved in discussions with the initiators of Science in Transition. The National Plan Open Science has initiated an investigation to explore how OS can be integrated within the evaluation of researchers and research proposals. A coalition of national stakeholders will work on this task by examining how alternative indicators (such as altmetrics) can be used for the assessment of researchers.

Table 11. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics in the Netherlands.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices identified	No policies/practices identified	The ambition 3.3.2 of the National Plan Open Science is to examine how OS can be integrated within the evaluation of researchers and research proposals. The stakeholders will investigate this by first examining alternative indicators (altmetrics) for the assessment of researchers.
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
No policies/practices identified	The AWTI recommends that scientific publication authors must also make the content of a scientific article comprehensible for the general public. However, some initiatives are emerging from researchers. 101 Innovations in Scholarly Communication, an initiative originating from Utrecht university library, has created a database of online tools for all phases of the research cycle, including dissemination. This user-friendly database can be used when searching for innovative dissemination tools. Some universities provide guidance on the use of innovative dissemination tools, such as social media, radio, television and blogs.	No policies/practices identified

¹⁵⁸ <https://101innovations.wordpress.com/>

¹⁵⁹ <http://uba.uva.nl/actueel/nieuws/content/2016/04/dare-altmetrics.html>

¹⁶⁰ <http://scienceintransition.nl/english>

United Kingdom

The UK is among the countries in which **OA policies** are widely implemented at national, institutional and funder levels.¹⁶¹ The UK government favours the **gold** road for OA to publications. The biggest research funding agencies (Wellcome Trust,¹⁶² Research Councils (RCUK),¹⁶³ Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE)) have also outlined and adopted OA policies, and require beneficiaries to provide OA to publications (and in some cases monographs and book chapters) as well as research data, whenever possible. JISC has funded major OA projects that encompass content, infrastructure, management and training, including SHERPA, ROAR, OpenDOAR, the Repository Support Project, the Open Repository Junction and ePrints UK. These stakeholders also provide funds to cover the costs of ACPs. Research institutions (such as universities) have their own OA policies and guidelines that provide information to researchers on how to comply with different OA requirements.¹⁶⁴ According to many interview respondents, the developments in the area of OA encouraged the government's proactive stance on OA.

There are also high levels of awareness about OA and ORD in the research community in the UK. Major stakeholders also take credit for it because their scholarly communications teams provide information through repositories list servers, detailed reports on offsetting agreements and various other issues. There are a few institutions such as University College London and University of Huddersfield that are developing local presses. In these cases, libraries provide a home for the university press, along with expertise and infrastructure.

HEFCE (Higher Education Funding council for England), Wellcome Trusts, Research Councils UK and Universities UK (membership organisation of universities across the UK) have all signed to the Concordat on **Open Research Data**.¹⁶⁵ This document was developed through consultations with the research community in the UK, and it outlines ten principles for research data sharing. While they encourage researchers to make data openly available,¹⁶⁶ the principles in the document also acknowledge legal, ethical and management issues in opening the data. Funders and universities are also developing the guidelines and trying to provide support to researchers to facilitate the process of opening data and drafting data management plans. Currently, 34 research institutions have adopted open research data policies.¹⁶⁷ However, the interviewees stated that in practice, while some funders require to share data openly, most universities struggle to comply with these requirements due to a lack of appropriate infrastructure.

In the area of **open peer review (OPR)** there are no national or organisational policies adopted in the UK. Nevertheless, there are discussions taking place in the scientific community addressing this topic, such as 'The future of scholarly scientific communication Conference'¹⁶⁸ that was organized in 2015 by the Royal

¹⁶¹ Asmah, J., "International Policy and Practice on Open Access for Monographs," 2014, <http://www.alyssaarbuckle.com/2017/01/25/on-international-policy-and-practice-on-open-access-for-monographs-by-josephine-asmah/>; European Commission, DG RTD, *Access to and Preservation of Scientific Information in Europe Report on the Implementation of Commission Recommendation C(2012) 4890 Final*.

¹⁶² <https://wellcome.ac.uk/funding/managing-grant/open-access-policy>

¹⁶³ <http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/documents/documents/rcukopenaccesspolicy-pdf/>

¹⁶⁴ For example, the OA policy of University of Leicester <http://www2.le.ac.uk/library/downloads/open-access/open-access-policy> or King's College London Research Publication Policy <http://www.kcl.ac.uk/governancezone/Assets/Research/Research-Publications-Policy.pdf>

¹⁶⁵ <http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/documents/documents/concordatonopenresearchdata-pdf/>

¹⁶⁶ <http://www.data.cam.ac.uk/funders>

¹⁶⁷ Horton, L and DCC (2016) 'Overview of UK Institution RDM Policies', Version 6 August 2016, Digital Curation Centre. Available at: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/policy-and-legal/institutional-data-policies>

¹⁶⁸ <https://royalsociety.org/~media/events/2015/04/FSSC1/FSSC-Report.pdf>

Society. As noted in section 4.1, the division on this topic is still strong in the scientific community and the practices are more often determined by journals and publishers than authors or reviewers. Some interviewees were hesitant to claim that the traditional peer review system does not work in the UK, although they acknowledged that OPR might be a way to address the issues around transparency and accountability associated with the current process. Many argued that there is a lot of experimentation around the peer review process. For instance, Wellcome initiated OpenResearch, an open post-publication peer review model shifting towards wholly open research publishing and direct assessment of outputs in various forms¹⁶⁹. Following the collaboration with ScienceOpen¹⁷⁰, a platform hosting its open access journal programme, UCL has set an ambition to establish an open research centre. As a result, UCL Press started to experiment with the open peer review infrastructure on the ScienceOpen platform to explore post-publication review workflows.¹⁷¹

Publons and PeerJ are trying to transform the culture through the adoption of open peer review.¹⁷² Many respondents viewed these activities positively, but indicated that a systematic analysis of what these experiments are and what is their relationship with various forms of research assessment is needed. Additionally, they revealed that if the results of these experiments were successful and published, it may help to trigger the political process around OPR.

Regarding **innovative dissemination** practices, a unifying national policy on research dissemination does currently not exist in the UK. Various funders, learned societies and universities provide guidance and support for researchers in their efforts to communicate their work and research results to the public. For example, Research Councils UK require researchers to demonstrate pathways to impact as a part of their research grant application process. Innovative dissemination usually constitutes one part of the overall communication strategy. Support is provided in terms of staff training on effective communication and social media use. Some organisations¹⁷³ have dedicated staff who advise researchers on communication and provide templates for dissemination plans. There are also universities that have community engagement initiatives¹⁷⁴. There is also a national body¹⁷⁵ that supports universities in public outreach efforts.

UK scientists have a growing interest in reaching audiences outside of those in academia with their research. JISC Ithaca survey of academics¹⁷⁶, published in 2015, revealed that there is growing interest from academics in reaching audiences outside of those in academia with their research. Comparing with the same survey conducted in 2012, they saw substantial increases in the share of respondents who indicated that professionals outside of academia, particularly undergraduate students, and the general public were very important audiences to reach with their research. Various large organisations are also interested in what kind of impact the research they fund has on different audiences. Interviews with stakeholders revealed that Wellcome, National Clinical Excellence and National Health Service (NHS) are interested in whether the research they fund have an impact on policy review.

¹⁶⁹ <https://wellcomeopenresearch.org>

¹⁷⁰ <https://www.scienceopen.com/>

¹⁷¹ <https://blogs.ucl.ac.uk/ucl-press/tags/post-publication-peer-review/#.WfsHNWiCyUk>

¹⁷² <https://publons.com/benefits/researchers>

¹⁷³ For example, Bournemouth University Research Blog <http://blogs.bournemouth.ac.uk/research/communicating-your-research/> or Scholarly communications Team at university of Edinburgh <http://www.ed.ac.uk/information-services/research-support/publish-research/scholarly-communications/innovations-in-schol-comms> or the National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/explore-it>

¹⁷⁴ For example, outreach work at the University of York <https://www.york.ac.uk/staff/external-relations/outreach/>

¹⁷⁵ National Co-ordinating Centre for Public Engagement <https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/explore-it>

¹⁷⁶ <https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6437/1/ithaca-survey-of-academics-2015.pdf>

There are quite a few networks that facilitate wider and more innovative dissemination strategies. Konfer is a platform that was started due to the collaboration between HEFCE and various other stakeholders working with the National Centre for Universities and Business.¹⁷⁷ The idea was to build a broker between the academic sector and the SME stroke industry to close the gap in the research pipeline and build further collaboration between universities, their research expertise, research outputs and the particular sector. JISC initiated Equipment Sharing, which lists the research equipment across the UK universities. Konfer linked this data to the locality, subject disciplines, making it much more accessible to a wider set of audiences. Additionally, it was reported that JISC is facilitating a national conversation, which pointed to the need to develop a national publication platform. That platform would provide information about innovative and quick publishing methods. It would also enable the work by collaborative means, for example through the use of new ways to publish nano publications or a smaller unit of disseminations like book chapters and other forms. JISC also initiated the Total Cost of Ownership project, which encourages institutions to openly publish the total cost of publications. There are 36 institutions currently involved in this initiative.

In the UK, initiatives have started to evaluate the use of **altmetrics** next to the use of other types of metrics. HEFCE, Wellcome Trusts, Research Councils UK, Universities UK and JISC set up a new Forum for Responsible Metrics¹⁷⁸ in 2016. The forum's goal is to support responsible use of research metrics in higher education institutions and across the research community in the UK. The forum is working to improve the data infrastructure that underpins the metric use. It has published a report with advice for the UK Higher Education Funding Bodies on the use of quantitative indicators in the assessment of outputs in REF2021.¹⁷⁹ The report comments on the possible avenues where altmetrics could be used as well as where it should not be used as a single indicator of impact.

Some funders, for example Wellcome Trust, have explored the potential value of altmetrics to find out early engagement of research in the policy sphere.¹⁸⁰

All these national and institutional initiatives illustrate the strong engagement by various stakeholders in the discussion on altmetrics. Many interviewees also emphasized that there are different data sources and measures that can be drawn upon to look at research activity and analyse it in new ways above and beyond the more traditional ways. It was reported that Institutional Repository Usage Statistics (IRUS-UK) is used by 90% of the UK institutions, and its data is harvested by PlumX and OpenAIRE. Additionally, it contributes to the establishment of the new metrics for OS. There are multiple case studies showing specific examples of the current use of IRUS-UK software by institutions.¹⁸¹ Nationally, there are various ways to measure research. For instance, the Higher Education Statistics Agency gathers a lot of data around the research process. The potential of altmetrics can be further explored through these different data sources.

Interviewed stakeholders agreed that the UK government and research funder landscape have a huge interest in altmetrics, but they are still investigating what would be the best approach to adopt them. There are many new opportunities to ensure that the system of research incentives, communication and funding

¹⁷⁷ <https://konfer.online/>

¹⁷⁸ <https://responsiblemetrics.org/>

¹⁷⁹ <http://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/policy-and-analysis/Documents/forum-for-responsible-research-metrics-response-to-REFconsultation2017.pdf>

¹⁸⁰ Dinsmore, A., Allen, L., Dolby, K., "Alternative Perspectives on Impact: The Potential of ALMs and Altmetrics to Inform Funders about Research Impact," *PLOS Biology* 12, no. 11 (2014), <http://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.1002003>.

¹⁸¹ <http://irus.mimas.ac.uk/support/supportmaterials/>

is more coherent and takes wider audiences and various inputs into account. In terms of the general direction of the UK research landscape, many interviewees claimed that as many major institutions are coming together under the umbrella of UK Research and Innovation due to restructuring of the entire landscape it will be easier to recognise and address issues and unintended consequences, which could arise due to the changes in some of the aspects of the established system.

Table 12. A non-exhaustive list of policies, initiatives or practices in OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics in the UK.

Open Peer Review	Innovative dissemination	Alternative metrics
National level/government initiated policies		
No policies/practices	No policies/practices	No policies/practices
Organisational level/Funders, learned societies and universities		
<p>Wellcome initiated OpenResearch, an open post-publication peer review model shifting towards wholly open research publishing and direct assessment of outputs in various forms. UCL Press experiment with the open peer review infrastructure on the ScienceOpen platform to explore post-publication review workflows. Publons and PeerJ are trying to transform the culture through the adoption of open peer review.</p>	<p>Konfer is a platform of HEFCE and other stakeholders, including the National Centre for Universities and Business, aimed at building a broker between the academic sector and the SME stroke industry to close the gap in the research pipeline and build further collaboration between universities, their research expertise, their research outputs and the particular sector. JISC also initiated Equipment Sharing, which presents a list of the research equipment across the UK universities, linking this data to the locality, subject disciplines, making it much more accessible to a wider set of audiences. JISC is also facilitating a national conversation, which pointed to the need to develop a national publication platform that would take into account more innovative and quicker ways to publish and to make it easier in terms of having the tools available. JISC also initiated the Total Cost of Ownership, which encourages institutions to openly publish the total cost of publications, and there 36 institutions currently involved in this initiative. Various approaches and guidelines on communication strategies exist at universities or funding organisations. They support researchers in developing their research communication strategies. In some cases, they also include guidance on the use of innovative dissemination tools, such as social media, radio, television and blogs.</p>	<p>Altmetrics is discussed mostly in the broader context of overall metrics. The Forum for Responsible metrics was established and has produced a report which includes a brief mentioning of altmetrics. The report advises for the use of altmetrics on a discretionary basis in informing impact assessment. However, the reports suggest that altmetrics should not be used for evaluation of outputs. Institutional Repository Usage Statistics (IRUS-UK) is used by 90% of the UK institutions, and its data is harvested by PlumX and OpenAIRE. UCL has set an ambition to establish an open research centre, which means that authors, editors, reviewers and readers will be able to make use of post-publication peer review, online commenting, individual article and author metrics such as altmetrics, citation and access tracking, ORCID integration, and a whole host of other benefits.</p>

6. Conclusions and next steps

This document outlines the main policies and initiatives across the EU as well as at the level of eight member states in key Open Science topics, including OA, RDM, OPR, innovative dissemination and alternative metrics. The report also addresses gender in research which is one of the key aspects in RRI. Through extensive desk research and literature review, the research team mapped the existing OS landscape in the EU and in the eight selected countries. The interviews conducted with national level stakeholders from different sectors as well as gender experts provided additional information on the

possible obstacles and enablers of OS and gender equality promoting policies and initiatives across countries.

Desk research and interview material point to an RRI landscape that is still developing across European countries. The European Commission is actively investigating and monitoring various aspects of Open Science through such initiatives as European Open Science Cloud and the Open Science Policy Platform. Several expert groups and working groups have been established by the EC to produce recommendations for several areas of Open Science that are still at nascent stages but already taken up by some researchers and other actors in the academic world.

Alongside high-level Commission efforts, there are bottom-up initiatives at national levels aiming to raise awareness and promote OA, RDM, innovative dissemination, alternative peer review methods and alternative impacts measurements. Some Member States are more advanced in their uptake of emerging OS-related initiatives into policies and mandates for OA and open research data. Others, on the other hand, have established non-binding declarations or recommendations.

The detailed analysis of eight countries presented in this report also illustrates varying levels of implementation of initiatives and policies across the three thematic areas of OpenUP. We could not identify any national level or government-initiated policies in open peer review or innovative dissemination. In some countries (Lithuania and Switzerland) the national entities responsible for the science and/or education policy have outlined science communication strategies. Innovative dissemination, although not the main aspect of the strategies, comprises a part of them, with an overall aim to promote scientific research to the public. We did not find any national level policies related to alternative metrics. Some early investigations of possible use of altmetrics for the evaluation of researchers are reported in the framework of the National Plan of Open Science in the Netherlands.

Under organisational level, more initiatives were found in the eight analysed countries under all OpenUP topics. These initiatives are mostly bottom-up coming from researchers, publishers, funding organisations, libraries and research organisations or learned societies. In addition, they are mostly implemented through various projects that aim to study and test different solutions. For example, some projects study in what ways and to what extent alternative metrics could be used when evaluating researchers. We also identified a funder and several publishers and journals testing possible options for OPR of post-publications.

Open Science and RRI have the potential to improve many important aspects of the review-assess-disseminate cycle of scholarly publishing. The publication reviewing processes could become more transparent by employing OPR practices; researchers could engage the public and achieve broader impact with innovative dissemination methods; and a wider array of research and researcher evaluation methods could make the assessment process more transparent and all encompassing. Research communities differ and one single approach cannot always be adapted across the distinct fields. Hence, as also indicated by the interview respondents, the actions should be directed towards raising awareness of OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics as well as studying and testing possible avenues for wider uptake and implementation.

This deliverable provides an overall synthesis of the results of the research activities conducted under WP7 and has laid the foundation for further work that will be conducted in OpenUP to produce the final policy recommendations. In the next months, the results from all the work packages of OpenUP will be coordinated and assembled into first drafts of policy reports (D7.3 and D7.4). These reports will provide brief overviews of key areas studied by OpenUP and present draft conclusions and recommendations for advancing OPR, innovative dissemination and altmetrics as well as advancing more gender balanced

research ecosystem. They will then be assessed by Strength, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats analysis to identify the key recommendations that could be implemented in different European countries and research systems. The final set of recommendations will be presented and validated in the final OpenUP workshop that will involve participants from national and EU level policy makers, funders, librarians, infrastructure providers, research council representatives and scientists.

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Annex 1.

Semi-structured interview questionnaire for national experts

1. Current status of Open Access (OA) and Open Research Data (ORD) policies - Introduction
1.1. Is there a growing understanding of OA and ORD within the research community? (Including researchers, funders, university administrators, libraries, etc).
1.2. What still prevents researchers from embracing OA and ORD management more?
2. Open Peer Review (OPR)
2.1. The established peer review process has received a lot of criticism, for instance, the process is criticized for being too lengthy, gender biased and often lacking accountability. Do you think OPR practices could help to address the shortcomings of the current peer review process? Why yes/not?
2.2. What hinders the uptake of OPR practices within the research community?
2.3. What aspects of OPR could be already promoted more in the academic and publishing sectors?
2.4. Are you aware of any national practices or initiatives that promote changes in peer review process?
3. Innovative dissemination
3.1. Are you aware of any strategies for research communication adopted nationally or by national funding agencies? Is innovative dissemination accounted for in these strategies?
3.2. What are the perceptions of researchers towards the use of innovative dissemination for research? Are there any discipline or generational differences?
3.3. Are there any channels of dissemination that could be used more by academics in order to reach a wider audience?
4. Alternative metrics
4.1. Are you aware of any attempts to take up altmetrics for research evaluation by universities, funders or other institutions?
4.2. What are the main barriers, in your opinion, that prevent researchers and other stakeholders from using altmetrics more actively?
4.3. What are the areas (for instance, researcher career advancement) in which altmetrics could be used more extensively?
5. Any further comments that you would like to make in terms of the topics we discussed today?

Semi-structured interview questionnaire for gender experts

1. Current status of progress towards gender equality in research and innovation
1.1. Has there been any significant progress made towards gender equality in research and innovation? Are you aware of any specific examples?

1.2. To what extent Open Science practices could help overcome gender inequalities in science? Or could it make the situation worse?
<p>2. Open peer review (OPR) – an umbrella term describing a variety of innovations which "open up" the traditional peer review process by modifying one or more aspects to make it more inclusive, transparent and/or accountable. It may include one or combine a variety of the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open identity: authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity; • Open report: review reports are published alongside the relevant article; • Open interaction: allows and encourages direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, as well as between reviewers; • Open participation: allows the wider community to contribute to the review process; • Open platform: review is de-coupled from publishing in that it is facilitated by a different organisational entity than the venue of publication; • Open pre-review manuscripts: manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g. via pre-print servers) in advance of any formal peer review procedures; • Open final-version commenting: review or commenting on final "version of record" publications.
2.1. What aspects of the established peer review process should be changed to address the existing gender bias?
2.2. To what extent can OPR help to overcome gender bias in the peer review process?
2.3. Are you aware of any practices or initiatives that seek to promote such changes in peer review process?
<p>3. Innovative dissemination – a planned process that involves consideration of target audiences and the settings in which research findings are to be received and, where appropriate, communicating and interacting with wider audiences in novel ways that will facilitate research uptake in decision making processes and practice.</p>
3.1. Would you agree that the use of certain platforms and tools may have negative effects for users of different genders or may be oriented towards a certain gender? (e.g. blogging might be more popular among male researchers)
3.2. To what extent is it important for researchers to consider gender dimension in their research dissemination efforts? How should this be implemented? (e.g. research funders could require four gender aspects, mentioned above, to be considered in their research dissemination policies)
<p>4. Alternative metrics – metrics and qualitative data that are complementary to traditional, citation-based metrics. They can include but are not limited to peer reviews, citations in public policy documents, discussion on research blogs, mainstream media coverage, bookmarks on reference managers and mentions on social networks.</p> <p>They can serve as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A record of attention; • A measure of dissemination; • An indicator of influence and impact.
4.1. How could research evaluation systems be improved to accommodate differences between female and male researchers?
4.2. Does the use of altmetrics have potential to improve the recognition and evaluation of female researchers?
<p>5. Any further comments that you would like to make in terms of the topics we discussed today?</p>